

MISSION ATLANTIC

Deliverable 3.2

Maps of present ecosystem pressures (fishing, shipping, pollution and other)

Version 5

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1. Executive Summary

The goal of this deliverable is to assess availability of FAIR spatial data about human activity using global datasets, and to identify obstacles (knowledge gaps) to mapping their corresponding environmental pressures at the scale of the Atlantic Ocean basin to support ecosystem-based management. It also provides advice towards improving mapping based on machine learning/artificial intelligence (AI). WP1 & 7 identified the sectors affecting the marine environment, the pressures they create, and the ecological characteristics affected. Eighteen sectors, with 19 associated pressures that could impact 25 different ecosystem components were identified. In this deliverable, only the widely distributed sectors relevant across the whole ocean are considered: fishing, shipping, aquaculture, oil exploitation, telecommunications, scientific exploration and seabed minerals.

Fishing intensity by main groups of fishing gears has been estimated by supervised classification of Automatic Identification System (AIS) data. These approaches have been able to distinguish between fishing and routing activity of individual vessels, while assigning up to 7 main fishing gear types. These are aggregated here into pelagic and bottom fishing activities to match the grouping of ecosystem components in these two groups. AIS data is most useful in the high seas since in coastal areas, smaller vessels do not require AIS, except in some regions of Europe. At the Canary Current Sea CS pelagic fishing shows the highest intensities around the Canaries and Cabo Verde archipelagos and all the way from western Sahara to Guinea-Bissau. On the contrary, bottom trawling concentrates closer to the coast off the coasts of northern Morocco and from western Sahara to Guinea-Bissau. At North Mid Atlantic Ridge CS scale, AIS data shows pelagic fishing is widely distributed except in the northern part, and bottom fishing seems to be concentrated on the Islands. At South Mid Atlantic Ridge CS, scale AIS data shows a wide distribution of pelagic fishing whereas bottom fishing seems to be poorly covered. At Brazilian Shelf CS scale, bottom and pelagic fishing are widely distributed on the area.

Shipping activities can be also inferred from AIS data. AIS systems reporting position through a satellite system are mandatory in all passenger ships irrespective of size, all vessels > 300 MT (gross) transiting international routes, and any cargo ship > 500 MT transiting within national waters. Global patterns reveal that highest shipping intensity is concentrated in coastal areas with narrow routes connecting Asia, Africa and Europe. Connectivity between these continents and America is broader with a medium intensity over large areas. This can be observed in the Europe connection with North America, Europe connection to South America, South Africa connection with South America and in the connection of Asia with North America and with Australia. At the Atlantic scale, the areas of highest shipping intensity are concentrated in European coastal waters. These higher intensity paths cross the southern Celtic Sea, Canary Current, and western Benguela Current case studies. The rest of the case studies also contain relatively high intensity paths, but not as extreme. The large area covered by high intensity paths in Canary Current, Benguela Current and South Brazilian Shelf case studies is noteworthy. The North Mid Atlantic has moderate intensity paths covering most of its area with two higher intensity paths crossing it. The Norwegian Sea and the South Mid Atlantic Ridge case studies include large areas of low shipping intensity.

We focus on three main sources of pollution: 1) Marine litter (widespread diffuse input), and in particular plastics (microplastics and macroplastics) and 2) Aquaculture platforms, as proxy of marine pollution sources (point source). feed, leading to major environmental concerns. 3) River discharges and nutrients (in between widespread and point source). Although river discharge and associated nutrients are a natural pressure in the coastal environment, anthropogenically polluted rivers can

significantly alter the health of marine ecosystems, especially as metallic pollutants are associated with sediments. Open litter data is sparse and focused mainly on European waters. Continuous Plankton Recorder, which can also be used to sample plastics, covers not only European waters, but also an important part of Northwest Atlantic area. After revising multiples sources of river discharges and nutrients discharges the WaterGAP 2.2d model and the Global River Water Quality Archive have been identified as the best sources of data at the Atlantic Ocean and global scales. Aquaculture data is very limited even in European open datasets and it can be addressed applying machine learning to satellite data.

Other seabed related data include oil exploitation, telecommunications, scientific exploration and seabed minerals. These data are integrated for European waters in EMODnet Seabed Habitats. In the Norwegian Sea, Celtic Sea, Benguela Current and South Brazilian Shelf additional local sources of oil exploitation data were available. In terms of telecommunications data, published data are predominantly landing stations and schematic routes. Regarding accurate spatial data on scientific surveys, only a few openly available sources have been identified at national and regional levels, and metadata are not standardised to be able to easily identify specific locations. Seabed mineral potential has been collated by EMODnet Seabed Habitats for most of the case study areas, except for the Benguela Current where local data were provided. Additional seabed mineral data were also provided for the South Brazilian Shelf, North Mid Atlantic Ridge and Benguela Current case study areas.

The term big data was coined to capture the meaning of the emerging trend in large and heterogeneous data exploitation. In addition to its sheer volume, big data exhibit other unique characteristics as compared with traditional data. For instance, big data are commonly unstructured and require real-time analysis. This development calls for new computer science related system architectures for data acquisition, transmission, storage, and large-scale data processing mechanisms. Big data techniques enhanced by machine learning methods can increase the use of such data and their applicability to ecosystem-based management. Machine learning has already proven its potential in marine science. It has been applied, for example, to fisheries forecasting, automatic classification of plankton samples, identification of schools by species of fish in acoustic survey data, litter classification and litter forecasting. However, if AI methods are not fit for purpose, then trade-offs to accomplish appropriate performances can be missed or overfitting can lead to over confidence on AI capacity if proper validation and ground truth verification is not performed.

This report highlights big data and machine learning-based datasets that are available to perform assessments at the level of the whole Atlantic Ocean. These datasets focus on the activities that impact open-ocean marine environments (shipping, fishing and litter) and coastal areas (river discharges and flows, and the growing aquaculture activity). The differentiation between fishing and non-fishing (e.g. travel) activities of fishing vessels as well as distinguishing the fishing gear is needed to go from mapping activities to pressures. For example, a fishing vessel en route to a fishing site will generate different levels and types of noise and emissions than it will whilst fishing. Noise and emissions will also differ depending on the fishing gear being used. Furthermore, the highest direct pressure exerted on the ecosystem occurs during fishing due to the removal of fish and bycatch, or litter generation from losing fishing gear and/or onboard activities. Members of ICES working group WGSHP are actively working on the development of a conceptual framework for mapping the pressures and impacts of shipping.

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3. Mission Atlantic Background

MISSION ATLANTIC develops and systematically applies Integrated Ecosystem Assessments (IEAs) in the Atlantic Ocean. IEAs enable identification of ecosystem components most at risk from natural hazards and the consequences of human activities. The project employs all available information on those sources, the pressures they impose and the ecosystem components that are affected, to identify the most important risk factors for sustainable development of the Atlantic Ocean. MISSION ATLANTIC develops and tests high-resolution numerical ocean ecosystem models, as well as employing advanced statistical approaches, artificial neural networks, and risk assessment methods in support of the IEA cycle. Cross-Atlantic seagoing activities will collect new observations on the shelf and open ocean, across benthic and pelagic biomes, to validate ecosystem models and explore the biogeography of plankton and fish communities. Advanced combinations of marine robotic solutions and acoustic sensors are further developed and deployed to provide new data and to deliver the next generation of autonomous systems in support of IEAs.

MISSION ATLANTIC aims at supporting the Atlantic Ocean research alliance and the implementation of the Galway and Belém statements. In 2017, the European Union, South Africa and Brazil co-signed the [Belém statement](#) on Atlantic Research and Innovation Cooperation for the South and tropical Atlantic and Southern Ocean. Following the Galway Statement, which focuses on North-Atlantic cooperation, the Belém statement furthers the integrated approach to research and development across the whole Atlantic Ocean and its bordering countries.

3.1. The role of this deliverable within Mission Atlantic

The goal of this deliverable is to map main present day ecosystem pressures in the Atlantic Ocean based on WP1 assessments. Fine-scale mappings of fishing and shipping pressures at seven case study sites are provided. Data and knowledge gaps that have been identified in areas such as coastal tourism, illegal fishing, habitat loss rates and point-source pollution (Halpern et al., 2012) are also addressed in this deliverable. The deliverable also assesses the availability of spatial information about human activity (fishing, shipping and pollution) and identify the obstacles (knowledge gaps) to map their corresponding environmental impacts on ecosystems (pressures) at the Atlantic Ocean basin scale to support ecosystem-based management. Integrated ecosystem assessments, which are at the heart of MISSION ATLANTIC, require knowledge and data on human activity and related pressures to link impacts to ecosystem state changes such as biodiversity loss. This provides a framework for a risk-based prioritization of links between pressures and ecosystem components, and for targeting research activities. Links between pressures and ecosystem state are evaluated in the context of multiple pressures. This report is based on the compilation and analysis of public datasets to fulfil the needs of the IEA cycle in each case study in MISSION ATLANTIC. The role of machine learning to generate these datasets or its potential for filling existing data and knowledge gaps is also discussed and its application has started to map aquaculture since is one of the areas where it has been identified that data is less available and where the literature of its mapping is sparse. This deliverable does not address emerging pollutants which are likely not possible to directly map during the project (Rocha et al., 2018; Gadelha et al., 2019; Ojemaye et al., 2019; Azaroff et al., 2020; Hassellöv et al., 2020; Zhu et al., 2021).

3.2. Contributors to this deliverable

Jose A. Fernandes¹, Maria Mateo¹, Yolanda Sagarminaga¹, Xabier Lekunberri¹, Thomas Furey², Maxim Kozachenko², Debbi Pedreschi², Roland Proud³, Clare Ostle⁴, Lynne Shannon⁵, Kerry Sink⁶, Lisa Skein⁶, Prideel Majiedt⁶, Vitor Alberto Souza⁷, Marinez Eymael Garcia Scherer⁷, Maria A. Gasalla⁸, Tiago Borges Ribeiro Gandra⁷, Sergio R. Floeter⁷, Jarbas Bonetti⁷, Eduardo Ramirez⁹, Marcos Llope⁹, Inês Gomes¹⁰, Diana Serrano¹⁰, Christopher Pham¹⁰, Pedro Afonso¹⁰, Andrew Brierley³, Guillem Chust¹

1. AZTI, Marine Research, Basque Research and Technology Alliance (BRTA), Sukarrieta, Spain
2. Marine Institute, Oranmore, Galway, Ireland
3. Pelagic Ecology Research Group, Scottish Oceans Institute, School of Biology, Gatty Marine Laboratory, University of St Andrews, St Andrews, UK
4. The Marine Biological Association, Plymouth, United Kingdom
5. University of Cape Town, South Africa
6. South African National Biodiversity Institute, South Africa
7. Federal University of Santa Catarina (UFSC), Brazil
8. University of Sao Paulo (USP), Oceanographic Institute, Fisheries Ecosystems Laboratory (LabPesq), Brazil
9. Instituto Español de Oceanografía (IEO-CSIC), Centro Oceanográfico de Cádiz (COCAD), Cadiz, Spain
10. IMAR Institute of Marine Research. Okeanos R&D Center. University of the Azores, Horta, Portugal

3.3. Acronyms and Abbreviations

ABNJ	Areas Beyond National Jurisdiction
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AIS	Automatic Identification System
ANP	Brazilian National Agency for Petroleum, Natural Gas and Biofuels Agency
ATLAFCO	Ministerial Conference on Fisheries Cooperation Among African States Bordering the Atlantic (or COMHAFAT)
BCLME	Benguela Current Large Marine Ecosystem
CCLME	Canary Current Large Marine Ecosystem
CECAF	Fishery Committee for the Eastern Central Atlantic
COREP	Regional Commission of Fisheries of Gulf of Guinea
CPR	Continuous Plankton Recorder
CS	Case Study(ies)
DECC	Department of Environment, Climate & Communications (Government of Ireland)
EBFM	Ecosystem-Based Fisheries Management
ECSA	European Subsea Cables Association
EC	European Commission
EMODnet	European Marine Observation and Data Network
FAIR	Findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations
FCWC	Fisheries Committee for the West Central Gulf of Guinea
GFW	Global Fishing Watch
ICCAT	International Commission for the Conservation of Atlantic Tunas
ICES	International Council for the Exploration of the Sea
IEA	Integrated Ecosystem Assessment
IOC	Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission
IPAS	Integrated Petroleum Affairs System
LME	Large Marine Ecosystem
MEOW	Marine Ecoregions of the World
ML	Machine learning
MOC	Meridional Overturning Circulation
MT	Metric Ton
NBA	National Biodiversity Assessment
NMAR	North Mid Atlantic Ridge (Case Study)
NS	Norwegian Sea (Case Study)
ODEMM	Options for Delivering Ecosystem-based Marine Management
RCP	Representative Carbon Pathway
RFMO	Regional Fisheries Management Organization
SAR	Synthetic Aperture Radar
SBB	South Brazilian Bight
SBS	South Brazilian Shelf (Case Study)
SRFC	Sub-Regional Fisheries Commission
SOMAR	South Mid Atlantic Ridge (Case Study)
VME	Vulnerable Marine Ecosystem

Maps of present ecosystem pressures (fishing, shipping, pollution)

- WGSHIP** Working Group on Shipping Impacts in the Marine Environment
- WP2** Work Package on Data technology and management for IEA
- WP3** Work Package on Pelagic Mapping: ecosystem, resources and pressures
- WP4** Work Package on Benthic Mapping: ecosystem, resources and pressures
- WP5** Work Package on Assessing state, drivers and tipping points

4. Atlantic Ocean mapping of human activities for ecosystem-based management

Adoption of ecosystem-based management (EBM) requires consideration of all human impacts. In WP1 & 7 an adapted ODEMM (Options for Delivering Ecosystem-based Marine Management; www.odemm.com) approach was used to link the sectors affecting the marine environment, the pressures they create, and the ecological characteristics affected (Knights et al., 2013; Knights et al., 2015; Pedreschi et al., 2019).

Figure 4.1. The sectors and pressures considered in this report in relation to pelagic and seabed ecosystem components as identified in WP1 & 7. Sectors, pressures and ecosystem components circled in red correspond to themes addressed in MISSION ATLANTIC WP3 and WP4.

MISSION ATLANTIC WPs 1 & 7 identified 18 possible case-study-level sectors, with 19 associated pressures that could potentially impact 25 different ecosystem components (Fig. 4.1). Presence or absence of pressures and corresponding interactions between them, lead to significant variability in ecosystem impacts across ecoregions (i.e., an ecologically distinct area) and management units (see D1.1 and D7.1 MISSION ATLANTIC deliverables). Impacts also vary significantly in the vertical domain due to environment-driven stratification of marine habitats. Therefore, in MISSION ATLANTIC the 25 ecosystem components were grouped in to pelagic (WP3) and seabed (WP4) components to map Atlantic Ocean ecoregions. A reduced set of widely distributed sectors relevant across the whole ocean are considered here: fishing, shipping, aquaculture, oil exploitation, telecommunications, scientific exploration and seabed mineral extraction (Fig. 4.1). Fishing and shipping are the main activities affecting pelagic ecosystems in high seas. Experts and stakeholders identified fishing and shipping as responsible for large proportions of the pressures in the individual case studies. The spatial extent of fisheries strongly overlaps with most ecosystem components. For shipping there is less information on spatial extent, resulting in potential under- or over-estimates of overlap with ecosystem components. In addition, two pressures of worldwide impact are being considered (litter and river discharges) where capacity to identify the sector producing them is limited, and which primarily originate on land.

The fishing sector is the source of several pressures, and has been identified as having the highest impact on marine ecosystems (WPs 1/7). However, associated pressures have varying levels of supporting evidence, for example there is robust evidence available for species extraction, bycatch, and abrasion, medium evidence for noise and litter, and limited evidence for abrasion. Although fishing is one of the most widespread activities by which humans harvest natural resources, its global footprint is poorly understood and has only just recently started to be directly quantified (Kroodsma et al., 2018). Shipping (maritime transport) contributes to marine litter, contaminants, and noise. Other activities contribute most significantly through contaminants, noise and litter. Exploited species are the most affected, but the distribution of impacts on ecosystem components is generally broad, affecting both biodiversity and habitats.

Fishing, shipping, and tourism/recreation were the sectors with the highest number of connections, which is mainly because these activities take place in almost all the study regions. Cumulated impacts of fishing, oil and gas, shipping, agriculture, and land-based industry on commercially exploited species and other ecosystem components via species extraction, bycatch, abrasion, noise and littering is a priority for future research.

4.1. Regional case studies

In MISSION ATLANTIC, seven case studies sites were selected to provide regional-level information to inform basin-scale models and biogeographic information. The CS are: the Norwegian Sea, Celtic Sea, Canary Current System, North Mid Atlantic Ridge, South Mid Atlantic Ridge, Benguela Current (focusing on the Southern Benguela) and South Brazilian Shelf (Fig. 4.2).

Figure 4.2. Boundaries of case studies across the whole Atlantic Ocean. Green lines delimitate Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) regions and red lines Large Marine Ecosystems (LMEs).

The Norwegian Sea (NS) ecoregion covers the Norwegian Sea and part of the Greenland Sea, separated by a deep-water ridge. It connects with the Faroes ecoregion to the southwest, the Icelandic Waters ecoregion and Greenland Sea to the west along the edge to the shallower Iceland Sea between the Faroe Islands, and northwards to Jan Mayen. To the south it borders the North Sea ecoregion, and to the east with the Barents Sea ecoregion. The Norwegian Sea ecoregion consists of two deep basins (between 3000 and 4000 m deep), the Norwegian Basin and the Lofoten Basin, separated by the Vøring Plateau (between 1000 and 3000 m deep). The Norwegian Sea is a transition zone for warm and saline Atlantic waters entering from the south, and cold and fresher Arctic waters entering from the north. The major current, the Norwegian Atlantic Current, is a poleward extension of the Gulf Stream and the North Atlantic Current that acts as a conduit for warm and saline Atlantic water from the North Atlantic to the Barents Sea and Arctic Ocean.

The Celtic Sea CS area covers the Celtic Sea (south of Ireland) and the west of Ireland Atlantic shelf. The focus is based on shared interest among the stakeholders, including key fisheries, future marine spatial planning efforts and potential conflicts among sectors. The boundaries are informed by the geographical extent of the Celtic Sea to the south, and including the western shelf region which covers the 'Biologically Sensitive Area'. The region is contained within the North Western Waters Administrative Region, and the ICES Celtic Seas ecoregion, but does not align directly with either. It includes parts of the Exclusive Economic Zones of Ireland, the United Kingdom and France.

The Canary Current Large Marine Ecosystem (CCLME) is one of the four major eastern boundary upwelling systems on the globe and the second most productive after the Humboldt Current. The CCLME extends from the Strait of Gibraltar (around 36°N 5°W) to Bissagos Islands off Guinea-Bissau (~11°N 16°W), embracing the coasts (5400 km) and Exclusive Economic Zones (EEZ, sea area of > 2 million km²) of Morocco, Western Sahara (Morocco), Mauritania, Senegal, the Gambia and Guinea-Bissau from north to south, and the Canary Islands (Spain) and Cabo Verde to the west.

The North Mid Atlantic Ridge (NMAR) case study geomorphology is characterized by the absence of continental shelf, the presence of narrow island shelves with steep slopes and over 100 seamounts identified. There is a large abyssal area, with depths averaging 3000 meters. Only 7% of the total area is shallower than 1500 and depths less than 600 m cover only about 1% of the entire of the Azorean EEZ (Peran et al., 2016). The oceanographic conditions are strongly influenced by the Gulf Stream western current. The Azores have been proposed as an oceanic confluence zone between the west and the east North Atlantic with a significant role in the ocean circulation and biological productivity (Caldeira and Reis, 2017). This area has been identified as having a distinctive phylogeography (Ávila et al 2009; Freitas et al. 2019), highly productive seamounts (Menezes, 2006; Morato et al., 2010; Carriço et al. 2019; Cascão et al. 2017), deep sea vulnerable marine ecosystems (Morato et al., 2021) and high biome diversity, including marine habitats for vulnerable or endangered marine megafauna (Afonso et al., 2020).

The South Mid Atlantic Ridge (SOMAR) area includes the three South Mid-Atlantic Ridge islands of St Paul's Rocks (i.e., St Peter and St Paul Archipelago), Ascension, and St Helena, located at the tropical and equatorial bands of the South Atlantic Ocean. The three islands have many aspects in common, including that they are very isolated and relatively small (Edwards & Lubbock, 1983a). They share many species, including some endemics that are exclusive of the three islands (Edwards & Lubbock, 1983b; Joyeux et al., 2001; Wirtz et al., 2014; Brown et al., 2019). A large-scale circulation feature in this basin is the subtropical gyre, with the Brazil Current at its western boundary, the South Atlantic Current at the southern limit, and the Benguela Current and the South Equatorial Currents at the eastern and the northern limit of the gyre (Stramma & England, 1999). Ascension and St. Helena Islands lay along the influence of the northward extension of the Benguela Current and the South Equatorial Current that flows south-westward. The tropical and subtropical regions of the South Atlantic cover the path of the return flow of the global scale circulation known as the Meridional Overturning Circulation (MOC).

The Benguela Current Large Marine Ecosystem (BCLME) is comprised of Northern and Southern Benguela ecosystems. The Southern Benguela extends south of Lüderitz (Namibia), along the west coast of South Africa and eastward as far as Port Alfred (South Africa), spanning two of the four subsystems of the broader Benguela Current Large Marine Ecosystem (Jarre et al., 2015). There is a limited amount of cross-boundary movement of some epipelagic species between Southern and Northern Benguela (Hutchings et al. 2009), but the strong and perennial upwelling cell off Lüderitz provides a fairly solid barrier to extensive mixing of pelagic stocks. Here, the focus is on the Southern Benguela system, and to linking to the existing National Biodiversity Assessment for South Africa (Sink et al., 2019) and for spatial marine planning and management in South Africa, the Southern Benguela case study is being considered to span the full extent of the South African marine territory.

The South Brazilian Shelf (SBS) cover the Rio Grande and the South-eastern Brazil ecoregions as described by the Marine Ecoregions of the World - MEOW (Spalding et al., 2007). It extends from the southernmost point of Brazil (Chuí) to Cabo Frio Cape, in Rio de Janeiro state (northern limit). The eastern boundary is defined by depth, covering only the continental shelf (depth < 200 m) to the coastline. SBS overlaps with focal sedimentary basins of the Brazilian National Agency for Petroleum, Natural Gas and Biofuels Agency (ANP), responsible for regulation, contracting, and oversight of commercial activities in the oil industry, and the region called South Brazilian Bight (SBB) (i.e., Gasalla & Rossi-Wongtschowki, 2004).

4.2. Ecoregions and biogeography

The case studies are distributed across multiple Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) regions (Fig. 4.3). Management of the FAOs is carried out by multiple Regional Fisheries Management Organizations (RFMOs). For example, FAO region 34 falls under several regional fisheries organizations and advisory bodies such as The International Commission for the Conservation of Atlantic Tunas (ICCAT), the Fishery Committee for the Eastern Central Atlantic (CECAF), the Sub-Regional Fisheries Commission (SRFC), the Fisheries Committee for the West Central Gulf of Guinea (FCWC), the Regional Commission of Fisheries of Gulf of Guinea (COREP) and the Ministerial Conference on Fisheries Cooperation Among African States Bordering the Atlantic (ATLAFCO, or COMHAFAT) (Arrizabalaga et al., 2019). In two instances, case studies sites span multiple FAO regions: North Mid Atlantic Ridge and South Mid Atlantic Ridge. However, species distribution often challenges the boundaries of management regions (Baudron et al., 2020).

Figure 4.3. Atlantic portions of global mesopelagic biogeographic maps published in 2017 by Proud et al. (left; based on acoustic backscatter), Sutton et al. (centre; fauna/expert) and Reygondeau et al. (right; biogeochemistry). These maps are redrawn from the source publications on to a common grid. Outline of Longhurst (2007) surface provinces are overlaid for reference. See also MISSION ATLANTIC MS3.1.

Large Marine Ecosystems (LMEs, Fig. 4.2) are coastal waters divisions that aim to have an ecosystem-based definition of regions for management and are commonly used in climate change research (Barange et al. 2014). Three case studies span across more than one LME: Norwegian Sea, Canary Current and Benguela Current. In contrast, open-ocean surface biogeographic regions (Fig. 4.3, see also MISSION ATLANTIC M3.1) typically arise from remote sensing data. Longhurst defined 56 provinces globally (22 in the Atlantic Ocean) in 4 Biomes (Westerlies, Trades, Polar and Coastal) based on satellite observations of surface primary production (frequency and magnitude) and regional oceanography. Various analyses of Atlantic fauna in the 2000s were directed at understanding animal biogeography in the basin, including work on reef fish (Floeter et al. 2008) and euphausiids (Letessier et al., 2009). Alternative biogeographic delineations that also consider deeper habitats (e.g., mesopelagic zone) have been recently proposed (Fig. 4.3): Proud et al. (2017) proposed a scheme based on water-column acoustic backscatter; Sutton et al. (2017) built a spatial classification by collating expert knowledge on distributional patterns of pelagic fauna or regions relative to environmental data felt to be important ecological drivers; and Reygondeau et al. (2018) proposed a biogeography based on biogeochemistry.

5. Methods

This study aims to identify the state of the art and knowledge gaps in mapping sectors and pressures with a focus on offshore regions and revising existing global datasets. It also provides advice towards improving mapping based on machine learning/artificial intelligence (AI). This information is contrasted and complemented with data from local sources targeting the seven regional case studies.

Information fusion collates, harmonizes, and integrates data and information from different sources and different granularities to provide continuous and complete data for analysis and modelling. This includes data from established sources including, for example, in-situ monitoring surveys, models and satellite imagery. A typical data fusion workflow includes collating and harmonizing the relevant data, running selected data fusion algorithms, visualizing the resulting data sets and associated uncertainty estimates in geo-information systems, and then exporting the resulting new data for further analysis. The terms ‘information fusion’ and ‘data fusion’ are typically employed as synonyms (Castanedo, 2013); but usually the term ‘data fusion’ is used for raw data (obtained directly from the sensors) while ‘information fusion’ is employed to define already processed ‘ready-to-use’ data (higher semantic level), as used in this project. The data is stored in a PostGIS spatial database that allows for more efficient information management and maintains the integrity of the spatial data. The development of routines in open-source software such as R and QGIS is enabling the generation of maps of each of the sectors producing anthropogenic pressures (Fig. 5.1).

Figure 5.1. Information fusion workflow including data collection (in multiple formats), ETL (extract, transform and load) process for storing all data in a spatial database (in PostGIS), and subsequent map generation during the data analytics process.

The information fusion in this report aims at integrating the most reliable, openly available data (i.e. FAIR data) with wide coverage of the whole Atlantic Ocean and/or worldwide. The FAIR concept, formally published by Wilkinson et al. (2016) to serve as a guideline to enhance the reusability of the data and their automatic location by the machines, is composed of the following concise and measurable principles: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR). These principles have been adopted among others by the H2020 Programme of the European Commission (2020) and they summarize them as follow:

- Findable: data must be discoverable with metadata, identifiable and locatable by means of a standard identification mechanism.
- Accessible: data and associated metadata, documentation and code must be deposited in public repositories that support open access.
- Interoperable: data and metadata must be interchangeable, reusable between different users and disciplines, compatible with open software and combinable with different datasets. The vocabulary of the metadata must comply with the standards.
- Reusable: specify how the data will be licensed to allow their maximum reuse, when and for how long they will be available, details of potential data embargo and restrictions on distribution.

There has been a remarkable rise in ocean observing systems, in parallel with the increasing production of different datasets during the last decades. This has increased the need for the adoption of FAIR principles (and automatization of data flows in ocean datasets) to ensure the use of ocean data for research, operational and commercial purposes (Tanhua et al., 2019).

This document revises FAIR datasets covering large areas of Atlantic Ocean that can support the ecosystem-management of the whole basin. This document also identifies some gaps for its application for pressures mapping.

6. Shipping

Shipping activities can be inferred from Automatic Identification System (AIS) data. AIS systems reporting position through a satellite system are mandatory in all passenger ships irrespective of size, all vessels >300 MT (gross) transiting international routes, and any cargo ship >500 MT transiting within national waters (Eguíluz et al., 2016).

The data analysed were provided by Exactearth (<http://www.exactearth.com/>) for the year 2014. Despite the data originating from several years ago, shipping main routes have a tendency not to change and intensity tends to increase except for temporal shocks (3-4 years) like the 2007 economic crisis or the recent COVID-19 pandemic. The global development of shipping largely reflects the patterns of global trade, with the volumes of transported goods having increased fourfold since the 1970s.

The data is provided in five categories: cargo, tank, passenger, fishing, and other. The cargo, tank and other were aggregated representing shipping activities producing pressures in the pelagic environment. Passenger vessels were kept separate since they might be a proxy for the tourism sector. Fishing data is addressed in the next section from a different source which differentiate fishing gears.

Global patterns reveal that highest shipping intensity is concentrated in coastal areas with narrow routes connecting Asia, Africa and Europe (Fig. 6.1). Connectivity between these continents and America is broader with a medium intensity over large areas. This can be observed in the European connection with North America, European connection to South America, South African connection with South America and in the connection of Asia with North America and with Australia. There is high coverage of medium-low intensity across the Atlantic Ocean.

A. Total shipping (vessel number per km2)

B. Commodities shipping (vessel number per km2)

C. Passenger (vessel number per km2)

Figure 6.1. Density of shipping activity in 2014. The vessel density is calculated as the number of vessels per square kilometre (the colour scale is logarithmic) per year. A) Total shipping activity considering cargo, tank, passenger, and other vessel type (fishing vessel have been omitted). B) Commodities shipping activity considering cargo, tank, and other vessel type (fishing and passenger vessels have been omitted). C) Passenger activity considering only this category of vessel type. The boundaries of the case studies are indicated by solid lines. Data source: Exactearth.

6.1. Shipping in the Atlantic Ocean

At the Atlantic scale, the areas of highest shipping intensity are concentrated in European coastal waters (Fig. 6.2). These higher intensity paths cross the southern Celtic Sea, Canary Current, and western Benguela Current case studies. The rest of the case studies also contain relatively high intensity paths, but not as extreme. The large area covered by high intensity paths in Canary Current, Benguela Current and South Brazilian Shelf case studies is noteworthy. The North Mid Atlantic has moderate intensity paths covering most of its area with two higher intensity paths crossing it. The Norwegian Sea and the South Mid Atlantic Ridge case studies include large areas of low shipping intensity.

Figure 6.2. Density of total shipping activity in 2014 (vessel number per km²). The vessel density is calculated as the number of vessels per square kilometre per year (the colour scale is logarithmic). Total shipping activity considering cargo, tank, passenger, and other vessel type (fishing vessel have been discarded). Data source: Exactearth.

Shipping activity for commodities follows the same patterns as for total shipping activity (Fig. 6.3a). Passenger activity is concentrated on the European coasts, with a strong intensity in the Norwegian Sea, the English Channel, and the south-western part of the Iberian Peninsula. In the western part of the Atlantic, this activity is mainly concentrated in the Caribbean Sea, part of the Gulf of Mexico and between Florida and the Dominican Republic. Finally, low activity is observed on the route via Cape Horn, the Falkland Islands and South Georgia and the South Sandwich Islands as well as off Morocco in the Canary Current (Fig. 6.3b).

Figure 6.3. Density of shipping activity in 2014. The vessel density is calculated as the number of vessels per square kilometre per year (the colour scale is logarithmic). A) Commodities shipping activity considering cargo, tank, and other vessel type (fishing and passenger vessels have been discarded). B) Passenger activity considering only this category of vessel type. The boundaries of the case studies are indicated by black lines. Data source: Exactearth.

This shipping activity can be compared with other data sources, such as vessel density from the public EMODnet Human Activities portal. The most recent data (from 2017 to 2020) on vessel density in the European Union expressed in hours per square kilometre per year can be viewed and downloaded from their portal. Although the years are not the same and the shipping activity is expressed in different units (in hours in EMODnet data versus numbers of vessels in Exactearth data), the routes of maritime activity match spatially (Fig. 6.4). In both data sources, the highest intensity paths cross the North Sea, the English Channel, Southern Celtic Sea, western Iberian coast, and the Mediterranean.

Figure 6.4. Vessel density (considering all type of vessels) in the European Union from different sources. A. Shipping density in 2017 expressed as hours per square kilometre per year. Data source: EMODnet. B. Shipping density in 2014 expressed as vessel number per square kilometre per year. The boundaries of the case studies are indicated by black lines. Data source: Exactearth.

6.2. Shipping in the Norwegian Sea

The highest shipping intensity is in coastal areas (Fig. 6.5a,b). This intensity decreases further from the land with the low to zero intensity in the majority of the region. The passenger routes is even more concentrated on the coastal line (Fig. 6.5c).

Figure 6.5. Density of shipping activity during 2014 in the Norwegian Sea. The vessel density is calculated as the number of vessels per square kilometre per year (the colour scale is logarithmic). A. Total shipping activity considering cargo, tank, passenger, and other vessel type (fishing vessel have been discarded). B. Commodities shipping activity considering cargo, tank, and other vessel type (fishing and passenger vessels have been discarded). C. Passenger activity considering only this category of vessel type. The boundaries of the case studies are indicated by black lines. Land is coloured in grey. Data source: Exactearth.

6.3. Shipping in the Celtic Sea

The highest shipping intensity is in the south and more strongly on the southeast of Celtic Sea case study region (Fig. 6.6). This pattern is similar for all the activities including passenger vessels. Passenger vessel density reflects the key ferry routes in the region. Some form of shipping takes place in all areas of the case study, with lower volumes along the Irish west coast. Higher volumes are associated with the locations of key ports (Fig. 6.7). Overall, shipping intensity throughout the Celtic Seas is the second highest out of the case studies examined.

Figure 6.6. Density of shipping activity during 2014 in the Celtic Sea. The vessel density is calculated as the number of vessels per square kilometre per year (the colour scale is logarithmic). A. Total shipping activity considering cargo, tank, passenger, and other vessel type (fishing vessel have been omitted). B. Commodities shipping activity considering cargo, tank, and other vessel type (fishing and passenger vessels have been omitted). C. Passenger activity considering only this category of vessel type. The boundaries of the case studies are indicated by black lines, land is indicated in grey Data source: Exactearth.

Figure 6.7. Locations of main ports in the region. Data from the European Atlas of the Seas.

6.4. Shipping in the Canary Current

The highest intensity of shipping traffic is concentrated in the northeast tip of the region, towards the Strait of Gibraltar (Fig.6.8a) as this is the main gateway into the Mediterranean. Passenger traffic (tourist cruises and ferries) also concentrate in this area (Fig. 6.8c). All the areas close to the coast show high intensity (Fig. 6.8a,b), but not on the coast itself. This is likely because AIS is used by larger vessels and coastal activity by smaller vessels (e.g., cargo ships < 500 MT, comparably very important in this part of the world) are not captured. Overall, shipping intensity throughout the Canary Current is the highest observed in the case studies examined.

Figure 6.8. Density of shipping activity during 2014 in the Canary Current. The vessel density is calculated as the number of vessels per square kilometre per year (the colour scale is logarithmic). A) Total shipping activity considering cargo, tank, passenger, and other vessel type (fishing vessel have been omitted). B) Commodities shipping activity considering cargo, tank, and other vessel type (fishing and passenger vessels have been omitted). C) Passenger activity considering only this category of vessel type. The boundaries of the case studies are indicated by black lines, land is indicated in grey. Data source: Exactearth.

6.5. Shipping in the North Mid Atlantic Ridge

The regional maritime space covered by the subdivision of the Azores is crossed by the most important and busy maritime routes to and from the Mediterranean, Africa and America, channeling traffic to northern Europe. Given its geographical remote setting, and when compared with previous case studies, the shipping traffic intensity is low overall in this region (Fig. 6.9a). In recent years there has been an increase in maritime traffic in the region and in the size of the cruise and cargo ships docking in the main Azorean ports (MSFD Report, 2020).

Figure 6.9. Density of shipping activity during 2014 in the North Mid Atlantic Ridge. The vessel density is calculated as the number of vessels per square kilometre per year (the colour scale is logarithmic). A) Total shipping activity considering cargo, tank, passenger, and other vessel type (fishing vessel have been omitted). B) Commodities shipping activity considering cargo, tank, and other vessel type (fishing and passenger vessels have been omitted). C) Passenger activity considering only this category of vessel type. The boundaries of the case studies are indicated by black lines, land is indicated in grey. Data source: Exactearth.

This activity is quite dispersed with some higher intensity towards the main ports of the archipelago (Fig. 6.9a-c). Between 2012 and 2016, 36.1% of the traffic registered in the Azores originated outside the region (international and national routes from mainland Portugal and Madeira archipelago). The islands with the highest percentage of traffic of international origin were: Flores (79.3%), followed by Faial (57.8%) and Santa Maria (18.6%). Foreign vessels which entered the marinas of the Azores, originated primarily from the Caribbean (17.8% overall and 57% of the vessels arriving on the island of Flores) followed by the USA (8.9%) and France (1.9%), the Canary Islands (1.1%) and mainland Spain (1.0%) (Costa et al., 2017).

6.6. Shipping in the South Mid Atlantic Ridge

The shipping traffic intensity is low in this region compared with previous case studies (Fig. 6.10a). The highest intensity is concentrated in the northern part of the region around Saint Peter and Saint Paul archipelago (Fig. 6.10a,b). Passenger shipping activity is not illustrated because such activity is less than one ship per square kilometre.

Figure 6.10. Density of shipping activity during 2014 in the South Mid Atlantic Ridge. The vessel density is calculated as the number of vessels per square kilometre (the colour scale is logarithmic). A) Total shipping activity considering cargo, tank, passenger, and other vessel type (fishing vessel have been omitted). B) Commodities shipping activity considering cargo, tank, and other vessel type (fishing and passenger vessels have been omitted). The boundaries of the case studies are indicated by black lines, land is indicated in grey. Data source: Exactearth.

6.7. Shipping in the Southern Benguela

Most of the Benguela Current case study area has high shipping intensity given its coastal nature and geographical location (Fig. 6.11). Shipping intensity is highest along the coast except for the north-western coast which has low intensity. The southern part of the area further from the coast show also lower intensity. Other sources of data (Walbridge, 2013; Halpern et al., 2015) show similar patterns of shipping intensity in this area (Fig. 6.11A). Shipping intensity in this case study is not as high as that documented in northern hemisphere regions, which applies to both the Atlantic and to a wider global scale (Gründlingh et al., 2006). However, ship traffic is still considerable and the country has several major ports, the majority of which are in the Western Cape province that has more than half of the 20 ports and harbours (Sink et al. 2019). Approximately 1000 bulk carriers, 1000 cargo vessels, 400 tankers, 1000 container vessels and several smaller vessels were estimated to pass Cape Point annually, as estimated in 1999 (State of the Environment Report - www.environment.gov.za/soer/nsoer/index.htm). Moreover, with approximately 120 million tons of oil and substantial volumes of bunker fuel passing through these waters every year (IMO, 2005), South Africa likely has one of the highest concentrations of oil tankers and cargo ships in the world.

Figure 6.11. Density of shipping activity during 2014 in the South Mid Atlantic Ridge. A) Data sourced from Walbridge (2013) and Halpern et al. (2015). B) Total shipping activity considering cargo, tank, passenger, and other vessel type (fishing vessel have been omitted). C) Commodities shipping activity considering cargo, tank, and other vessel type (fishing and passenger vessels have been omitted). D) Passenger activity considering only this category of vessel type. The boundaries of the case studies are indicated by black lines, land is indicated in grey. Data source: Exactearth, for which the vessel density is calculated as the number of vessels per square kilometre (the colour scale is logarithmic).

6.8. Shipping on the South Brazilian Shelf

The South Brazilian Shelf shows medium fishing intensity in comparison to the other case studies. Within the case study region, shipping traffic is present throughout the region (Fig. 6.12a,b) with the highest intensity close to the coast and in the northern part of the region. In this northern part of the region and in the southern area close to the coast passenger vessel intensity is higher (Fig. 6.12c).

Figure 6.12. Density of shipping activity during 2014 on the South Brazilian Shelf. The vessel density is calculated as the number of vessels per square kilometre (the colour scale is logarithmic). A) Total shipping activity considering cargo, tank, passenger, and other vessel type (fishing vessel have been omitted). B) Commodities shipping activity considering cargo, tank, and other vessel type (fishing and passenger vessels have been omitted). C) Passenger activity considering only this category of vessel type. The boundaries of the case studies are indicated by dashed lines, land is indicated in grey. Data source: Exactearth.

The shipping high intensity areas are related to lanes linking the main ports in SBS. At SBS northern areas, some hotspots can be found near oil and gas exploration platforms (Figure 6.13). Coastal areas (depth < 100 m) are highly used for shipping at SBS.

Figure 6.13 Density of shipping activity during 2019 on the South Brazilian Shelf. The vessel densities were reclassified to ordinal scale (Very Low - High). Main ports are marked as points. The boundaries of the case studies are indicated by dashed lines. Data source: MarineTraffic.

7. Fishing

Fishing intensity by main groups of fishing vessel/ gears types can be estimated by supervised classification of vessel position and speed data. Here we used fishing intensity estimates from the Global Fishing Watch initiative (GFW) (Kroodsma et al. 2018), who applies machine learning algorithms to data from Automatic Identification Systems (AIS), Vessel Monitoring Systems (VMS), and vessel registries. This machine learning approach has been able to distinguish between fishing and routing activity of individual vessels, while using pattern recognition to differentiate seven main fishing gear types at the Atlantic Ocean scale (Taconet et al., 2019). The seven main fishing vessel types considered are: trawlers, purse seiners, drifting longliners, set gillnets, squid jiggers, pots and traps, and other. In this work we have aggregated these into pelagic and bottom fishing activities to align with our grouping of ecosystem components (pelagic and seabed; Fig. 7.1).

The GFW data has some limitations. First, AIS is only required for large vessels. The International Maritime Organization requires AIS use for all vessels of 300 gross tonnage and upward, although some jurisdictions mandate its use in smaller vessels. For example, within the European Union it is required for fishing vessels at least 15m in length. This means that in some areas the fishing intensity estimates will not include the activity of small vessels operating near shore. Another limitation is that the AIS can be intentionally turned off, for example, when vessels carry out illegal fishing activities (Kurekin et al. 2019). Finally, in the GFW dataset, vessels classified as trawlers include both pelagic and bottom trawlers. As trawlers are included in the bottom fishing category, it is highly likely that the data overestimates the effort on the seafloor and underestimates it on the water column.

A. Pelagic fishing (hours per km²)

B. Seabed fishing (hours per km²)

Figure 7.1. Total fishing hours per square kilometre in 2020 (the colour scale is logarithmic). A. Pelagic fishing. B. Seabed fishing. The boundaries of the case studies are indicated by black lines. Data source: Global Fishing Watch.

7.1. Fishing in the Atlantic Ocean

At the Atlantic scale, mapping based on AIS data represents offshore fishing, because in many coastal areas smaller vessels do not require AIS to operate. The exception is in European waters where some smaller vessels use AIS and the available data make coastal fishing patterns clearer, yet not complete. Similar intensity patterns can be seen in regional case studies of Africa, South and North America where much of the fishing is concentrated nearshore. High seas within and around the North Mid Atlantic Ridge, Canary Current and South Mid Atlantic Ridge also concentrate areas of high pelagic fishing intensity (Fig. 7.2).

Figure 7.2. Total fishing hours per square kilometre in 2020 (the colour scale is logarithmic). A. Pelagic fishing. B. Seabed fishing. The boundaries of the case studies are indicated by black lines. Data source: Global Fishing Watch.

7.2. Fishing in the Norwegian Sea

At Norwegian Sea CS scale fishing activity concentrates on coastal areas and southwestern areas in the middle of the region (Fig. 7.3).

A. Pelagic fishing (hours per km²)

B. Seabed fishing (hours per km²)

Figure 7.3. Total fishing hours per square kilometre in 2020 (the colour scale is logarithmic). A. Pelagic fishing. B. Seabed fishing. The boundaries of the case studies are indicated by black lines. Data source: Global Fishing Watch.

7.3. Fishing in the Celtic Sea

The Celtic Sea and west of Ireland have highly diverse mixed fisheries. Twelve demersal TAC species dominate the landings in the Celtic Sea (hake, anglerfish, megrim, whiting, Nephrops, haddock, cod, pollack, sole, ling, saithe, and plaice; ICES 2021). These are landed by six nations (Ireland, France, United Kingdom, Spain, the Netherlands, and Belgium), using 29 main métiers (ICES, 2021). The spread of effort between the nations from 2014-2018 within the Irish EEZ can be seen in Figure 7.4.

Figure 7.4.: Distribution of international fishing effort in the Irish EEZ by country 2014-18. Taken from Gerritsen, & Kelly (2019).

Otter trawlers and demersal seiners account for the majority of the fishing effort, with large mixed bottom-trawl fisheries targeting benthic species, *Nephrops*, and gadoids. The species composition of these mixed fisheries tend to vary, depending on the area and the countries involved in the fishery (ICES 2021). The pelagic fisheries (Fig. 7.5) account for the largest catches (by weight) in the Celtic Seas ecoregion (larger than the study area) and consist of mid-water trawl fisheries for blue whiting, mackerel, horse mackerel, herring, boarfish, and sprat (ICES, 2021). The Irish fishing fleet is highly polyvalent and diverse with around 1500 < 10 m and 500 ≥ 10 m active vessels. The numerous ≥10m vessels target a wide variety of species using several types of gear. Small vessels (< 10 m) operate inshore, typically targeting shellfish with pots or demersal fish with nets (ICES, 2021). Given their high numbers, the <10m vessels represent an important social group, however as they are not required to have VMS, we are unable to quantify their effort. The combined Irish and international activity results in an overall high spatial coverage, with much effort concentrated around the shelf edge, while passive gears tend to be concentrated closer to shore (Fig. 7.4).

Figure 7.5. Total fishing hours per square kilometre in the Celtic Sea (the colour scale is logarithmic) from AIS data. A) Pelagic fishing. B) Seabed fishing. C) Passive fishing corresponds to pots and traps, set gillnets and fixed gears. Data source: Global Fishing Watch.

7.4. Fishing in the Canary Current

The Canary Current Sea CS pelagic fishing shows the highest intensities around the Canaries and Cabo Verde archipelagos and all the way from western Sahara to Guinea-Bissau. On the contrary, bottom trawling concentrates closer to the coast (shelf and slope) off the coasts of northern Morocco and

from western Sahara to Guinea-Bissau (Fig. 7.6). Little bottom trawl activity is seen around the archipelagos, due to their narrow and rocky continental shelves. It is worth noting that the AIS footprint, only captures big (industrial) fishing boats and overlooks artisanal vessels, which are very numerous and important in this region.

Artisanal fishing vessels lack AIS or VMS systems and their footprint cannot be tracked. However, this fleet is extremely important in countries such as Senegal and Mauritania. The same applies to the Canary Islands, where most vessels are below 12 m, although their social and economic importance is comparatively lower here.

VMS information does indeed exist for Morocco and for those European fleets that operate in these waters under Sustainable Fisheries Partnership Agreements (SFPAs)¹ between the EU and the corresponding west Africa countries. The latter currently include all CCLME countries, namely Morocco, Mauritania, Senegal, The Gambia, Guinea-Bissau and Cabo Verde. This information should be available upon request to the corresponding countries (e.g., Morocco or European countries). Russia and China also operate in the CCLME through bi-lateral agreements.

Figure 7.6. Total fishing hours per square kilometre in 2020 (the colour scale is logarithmic). A) Pelagic fishing. B) Seabed fishing. C) Unknown fishing: the fishing gear is not identified. The boundaries of the case studies are indicated by black lines. Data source: Global Fishing Watch.

¹ https://ec.europa.eu/oceans-and-fisheries/fisheries/international-agreements/sustainable-fisheries-partnership-agreements-sfpas_en

7.5. Fishing in the North Mid Atlantic Ridge

At North Mid Atlantic Ridge CS scale AIS data shows pelagic fishing is widely distributed except in the northern part (Fig. 7.7). Bottom fishing seems to be concentrated on the Islands. Eastern pattern of high bottom fishing might be an artifact of the AIS data classification, likely because pelagic trawlers are included in this group.

Figure 7.7. Total fishing hours per square kilometre in 2020 (the colour scale is logarithmic). A) Pelagic fishing. B) Seabed fishing. C) Unknown fishing: the fishing gear is not identified. The boundaries of the case studies are indicated by black lines. Data source: Global Fishing Watch.

Although fishing is known to occur throughout the NMAR area, most of our knowledge comes from what is happening inside the Azores EEZ. Currently, the Azorean fishery is composed of four main fleets: i) a pole-and-line tuna fishery, ii) an artisanal purse seining fishery for small pelagic species, iii) bottom longline and handline targeting demersal species and deep-sea species. The regional artisanal fleet also includes fishing for commercial coastal invertebrates, squid fishing and an important recreational fishing activity (Morato, 2012).

Demersal and deep-sea bottom longline fisheries are the main fisheries in the Azores regarding weight and value landed, number of vessels and jobs generated, operating throughout the year from coastal areas to offshore seamounts (Pinho & Menezes, 2006; Carvalho et al., 2011). Despite the size of the Azores EEZ being about 1 000 000 km², the average depth is around 3000 m, with depths less than 600 m covering only about 1% of the entire EEZ (7000 km²; Menezes 2003). This makes bottom/seabed (term used in fig 5.6) fishing grounds relatively small and geographically dispersed, conditioned by depth, currents and the bottom complexity. Given that the vast majority of the regional fleet, due to its size, operates near the islands and small seamount (about 80% operates at a distance less than 30 nm; SRMCT, 2018), most vessels do not carry AIS transmitters (Automatic Identification System). This system is only mandatory in the region for fishing vessels greater than 15 m. For these reasons, the fishing effort reported here is underrepresenting the regional fishing effort and captures mainly the industrial fishing fleet operating outside the 100 nm.

In 2018, the active fleet was composed of 463 vessels, representing 80% of the regional fishing fleet. It is predominantly composed by small vessels, < 12 m in length (Silva & Pinho, 2007). Total landings contribute to about 40% of the entire weight landed in the Azores and represents about 75% of the total landed value. Large-scale or semi-industrial vessels (> 16 m) only represents 5% of the entire regional fleet (SRMCT, 2018). Deep-sea trawling has been banned in the region since 2005 (EC 1568/2005).

Pelagic fishing in the region includes both the (mostly) regional pole-and-line fleet targeting tunas and surface longliners targeting swordfish and blue sharks which are mostly coming from Spain and mainland Portugal. Both pole-and-line and surface longline fishing occur throughout the NMAR but with distinguished areas depending on the vessel flag. While pole-and-line fishing occurs mostly around seamounts located inside the Azores EEZ, surface longliners from Spain are obliged to fish outside the 100 nm. Although surface longline vessels from mainland Portugal are allowed within the 100 nm, they mostly fish outside of this area.

7.6. Fishing in the South Mid Atlantic Ridge

At South Mid Atlantic Ridge CS scale AIS data shows a wide distribution of pelagic fishing whereas EEZ and bottom fishing seems to be poorly covered by AIS (Fig. 7.8).

Figure 7.8. Total fishing hours per square kilometre in 2020 (the colour scale is logarithmic). A. Pelagic fishing corresponds to trollers, squid jigger, pole and line, purse seines, tuna purse seines, other purse seines, set longlines and drifting longlines. B. Unknown fishing: the fishing gear is not identified. The boundaries of the case studies are indicated by black lines. Data source: Global Fishing Watch.

There are fishing hotspots close to the boundaries of the 3 islands EEZs that are not neighbouring the mid-Atlantic ridge itself (Taconet et al., 2019). The region south of St Peter and St Paul archipelago (ASPSP) and west of Ascension island is specially targeted by the international tuna fishing industry which also targets swordfish and sharks, including both surface longliners and some purse-seiners. Bigeye tuna is the principal target species, however, yellowfin tuna, white albacore, swordfish, skipjack, blue and other marlin species and tuna have also been caught (Rowlands et al 2019). Bycatch fish species, most notably blue sharks and other shark species have been dominant in the longline fisheries (Irving, 2015). Ascension sits at the south-eastern edge of the area of highest mean effort (35,000–47,000 estimated hooks set per month) from ICCAT data. This region of high effort extends north west of the EEZ to $\sim 10^{\circ}\text{N}$, 35°W . Hotspots of fishing effort appear close to, or intersecting with the EEZ regardless of whether a licensed fishery was in operation or not (Rowlands et al, 2019). Squid jiggers also occur in the region (Taconet et al., 2019).

In the Brazilian EEZ, fisheries including commercial and recreational are also common off ASPSP, just outside the exclusion zone (marine protected area). Commercial fishing is conducted all year round. Target species are *Thunnus albacares*, *Acanthocybium solandri*, *Elagatis bipinnulata*, *Cypselurus cyanopterus* (bait) and *Ruvettus pretiosus*. Reef fish such as *Caranx lugubris*, *Carangoides bartholomaei*, *Sphyrnaena barracuda*, *Canthidermis sufflamen* are also common, as well as lobsters (Viana et al., 2015; Francini-Filho et al., 2018).

7.7. Fishing in the Southern Benguela

Benguela Current CS focuses on very coastal areas off South Africa, where AIS data coverage is lower (Fig 7.9). However, local partners have provided data. Pelagic fishing in South Africa comprises four fishing sectors: Tuna Pole, Pelagic Long-lining, Small Pelagic purse seine, and Midwater trawling. Midwater trawling is carried out by one ship with dual rights to conduct demersal trawling.

Figure 7.9. A) Pelagic fishing. B) Seabed fishing. C) Pelagic fishing corresponds to trollers, squid jigger, pole and line, purse seines, tuna purse seines, other purse seines, other seines, set longlines and drifting longlines. Data source: Global Fishing Watch.

The South African tuna pole fishery largely operates off the west coast of South Africa, within the 200 nautical miles fishing zone, particularly between 29° and 32°S, targeting southern Atlantic tuna stocks (Fig. 7.10). Less than 1% of the tuna pole catch is caught eastwards of the 20°E longitude line. Tuna fishermen focus their effort along the shelf edge with highest reported effort between Lamberts Bay and the southern tip of the Agulhas Bank and also in the vicinity of the submarine bank known as Childs Bank. Shannon *et al.* (1989) report that the Cape Valley and the Cape Canyon are important tuna fishing areas because of upwelling and the position of the oceanic thermal front close to the coast in these areas. Many of the pelagic longline vessels are reported to fish near the edge of, or on, the continental shelf (Petersen *et al.* 2009c).

Figure 7.10. Map of scaled tuna pole fishing intensity. Point data collated to a coarse 50nm grid was received from the then Department of Agriculture, Forestry and Fisheries (DAFF; now the Department of Forestry, Fisheries and the Environment, DFFE) national fisheries department for the period 2007-2016. The total catch records were allocated to a centroid in each grid square and 0 values were allocated to all non-fished grid squares. Natural neighbours interpolation was undertaken for marine areas. Extremely low values with <10,000 kg total catch over the 2007-2016 period were excluded. The equation $100 * n / n99$ method used to deal with skewed distributions and resulting values over 100 were reclassified as 100. Values were modified using the boundaries for marine protected areas where tuna pole is excluded under legal regulations.

Bottom fishing is mostly trawling and long-lining. Data for South Africa’s demersal trawl industry was updated and is publicly available on the online platform for the South African Environmental Observation Network (Currie et al., 2021). The demersal longlining fishery operates along the west and south coast with effort concentrated along the shelf edge (Fig. 7.11). Highest effort has been recorded in the vicinity of the Cape Valley off Cape Point, near Cape Canyon off Cape Columbine, offshore of Tsitsikamma and near Port Elizabeth.

A. Demersal Longline Intensity (annual average catch)

B. Seabed fishing (hours per km2)

Figure 7.11. A. Map of scaled intensity of demersal hake longlining for period 2000 – 2017 presented as annual average catch in kilograms. B. Seabed fishing corresponds to trawlers, fixed gears, dredge fishing set gillnets, pots and traps (data source: Global Fishing Watch).

7.8. Fishing on the South Brazilian Shelf

In the Brazilian Shelf CS, the main industrial fishing types (according to number of vessels) are trawling and traps (for bottom fishing) and gillnets and pelagic longline (for pelagic). Longline fishery is primarily directed to the capture of albacores, swordfish and sharks (Fiedler, 2017). Longline fishery is held on the continental shelf slope (150 - 1500 m depth) with hotspots at south of SBS, along Rio Grande do Sul state (Figure 7.13). Pelagic gillnet fishery is the main type in SBS and it is spread all along SBS, mainly near the 50 m isobath, with a deeper hotspot at the southern SBS (Fig. 7.12 & 7.13).

Figure 7.12. Total fishing hours per square kilometre in 2020 (the colour scale is logarithmic). A. Pelagic fishing corresponds to trollers, squid jigger, pole and line, purse seines, tuna purse seines, other purse seines, other seines, set longlines and drifting longlines. B. Bottom fishing corresponds to trawlers, fixed gears, dredge fishing, set gillnets, pots and traps. D. Unknown fishing: the fishing gear is not identified. The boundaries of the case studies are indicated by dashed lines. Data source: Global Fishing Watch.

At SBS the trap fishery's main target species are the royal crab. This industrial fishery type occurs mainly in shallow waters (depth < 50 m) in the north (São Paulo and Rio de Janeiro states). The trawling fishery (second in number of vessels) in SBS target species varies according to the trawling system used (double-rig, pair, and stern trawling) and the season. It is spread all along the SBS, at depths from 10 to 100 m (Fig. 7.12 & 7.13).

Figure 7.13. Density maps for the main industrial (number of vessels) fishery types at the South Brazilian Shelf. A) Gillnet pelagic fishery, B) Seabed trawler fishery, C) Pelagic Longline and D) Benthic traps. Data source: Brazilian industrial fishery satellite monitoring program (PREPS) at www.preps.gov.br/web

8. Pollution

There are several marine pollutants that can be mapped across the Atlantic, each have different impacts on the environment they occupy, and consequences for marine life. In most cases, there are still many unknowns about the impact, for example, although we know that plastics are everywhere and that organisms are ingesting them, but more knowledge is needed about the harm they might be causing and their toxicity. Globally, over 370 marine species are known to have been directly affected by litter through ingestion or entanglement (CBD, 2012). Benthic fauna and habitats are also threatened by litter (particularly fishing gear and plastic bags), through smothering and abrasion (Brown and Macfadyen, 2007; Gregory, 2009). Floating debris can also aid in alien species invasions, providing hard substrates for colonisation and acting as rafts for transportation (Winston, 1982; Barnes, 2002; Derraik, 2002; Gregory, 2009; Katsanevakis et al., 2007; Gall and Thompson, 2015). Turner, Ostle and Wootton (2021) recently demonstrated that many microplastic flakes are from paint; these paint flakes often contain toxic elements that could be harmful to organisms ingesting them. Other forms of microplastic include microfibers that are released when we wash our clothes (Browne et al., 2011). Microplastics also originate through the fragmentation of macroplastics by mechanical action and UV weathering (Maes et al., 2017) New techniques are in development which can detect plastics from space using satellite imagery (Biermann et al., 2020), however this is very much in development and at present only possible with high resolution images from coastal regions.

In this deliverable, we focus on three main sources of pollution:

- 1) Marine litter, and in particular plastics (microplastics and macroplastics). Marine litter is any material that is discarded, disposed of, abandoned or transported to the marine and coastal environment (Werner et al. 2016). Marine litter is pervasive; readily transported, produced by all sectors and presents risk to all habitats and species.

- 2) River discharges and nutrients. Although river discharge and associated nutrients are a natural feature in the coastal environment, anthropogenically polluted rivers can significantly alter health of marine ecosystems, especially as metallic pollutants are associated with sediments (Stoichev et al., 2004).

- 3) Aquaculture platforms, as proxy of marine pollution sources. Aquaculture generates point source waste, and by-products from the natural food as sources of nutritional inputs for most farmed aquatic organisms, and at present there is an increasing use of pelleted feed in modern aquaculture, leading to major environmental concerns (e.g. Edwards, 2015; Shannon and Waller, 2021).

8.1. Marine litter

Global litter and plastic distribution data can be visualized using the interactive map available at LitterBase online portal (<https://litterbase.awi.de/litter>; Tekman et al., 2022). However, this data is not yet openly available for downloading. Global composition of marine litter is mostly derived from plastic.

Open marine litter data for European waters can be gathered from the EMODnet Chemistry portal (<https://www.emodnet-chemistry.eu/>), which compiles data on marine litter in beach, water bodies and sea floor on a global scale, covering a temporal range from 2001 to 2020 (Fig. 8.1). The marine litter on the beaches corresponds to macro-litter (> 2.5 cm) collected during Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD) monitoring protocols, but also from other monitoring surveys, research, and cleaning operations. A continuous gradient of this macro-litter is observed along the entire North Atlantic coastline (from southern Spain to southern Sweden). In southeast Greenland, Iceland, and Finland, marine litter is scarce or undersampled or underreported, while in Ireland and the United Kingdom, litter is abundant. Macro-litter is also found in beaches of Macaronesia (Azores, Madeira and Canary Islands). In the Azores archipelago (NMAR case study), fisheries observers have been monitoring the abundance of floating litter between 2015 and 2021 with average densities of 1.39 ± 0.14 items.km⁻² (Chambault et al., 2018). The micro-litter found in water bodies has been collected during scientific monitoring carried out mainly on the Cantabrian coast between 2011 and 2020. As such, the current distribution maps reflect not just the litter found, but the sampling effort employed (no litter may be due to a lack of sampling rather than a lack of litter).

Figure 8.1. Marine litter abundance based on the EMODnet Chemistry data portal. Litter abundance on: beaches collected by observers (green dots), micro-litter in water bodies collected by Neuston nets (pink dots), and litter from the seabed collected by demersal trawl nets (blue lines).

8.1.1. Pelagic marine litter

The Continuous Plankton Recorder (CPR) is a towed marine sampler, that is voluntarily towed behind ships of opportunity at a water depth of ~7 m, which due to the wash of the ship samples the top ~20 m surface layer. Each CPR sample represents 10 nautical miles of tow, for a detailed methodology on using the CPR data please refer to Richardson et al. (2006). The CPR has been designed to capture the plankton within the surface waters, however often it captures other particles that reside in the surface waters such as plastics. Due to the longevity, consistency in sampling, and careful curation of CPR samples, the CPR has been used to create time series of marine plastics.

Figure 8.2. Macro and microplastics in the North Atlantic from the Continuous Plankton Recorder (CPR). Subplot A: Macroplastic entanglement in the 1957-2016 period, with colours representing the different items entangled. Subplot B: Microplastic presence (red) and absence (blue) within the CPR samples from 2004-2018.

In the North Atlantic, data from the CPR have been used to map the distribution of macroplastics (Fig. 8.2a) and microplastics (Fig. 8.2b). Here, macroplastics are defined as plastic pieces > 5 mm. The CPR captures plastics on the body of the CPR; these are often macroplastics and are an indicator of entanglement risk within the area. When an entanglement occurs on the CPR body it is noted within the tow log of the CPR. The cases of macroplastic entanglement on the CPR have been collated and published in Ostle et al., (2019). To normalise the counts of macroplastic entanglement, we used a percentage frequency of occurrence calculation = (number of entanglements/ number of tows) × 100. These cases are mapped in figure 6.2a with the colour representing the type of macroplastic entanglement. The map demonstrates that areas close to rivers and densely human populated areas have the highest concentrations of macroplastics, and therefore represent hotspots for entanglement. The items that were most likely to cause entanglement and were more abundant in these records,

were those associated with fishing gear. Microplastics are defined as plastic pieces < 5 mm. The term microplastics was first coined in a paper written by Thompson et al. (2005), where an increase in microplastic was demonstrated since the 1960s using stored CPR samples. Within the routine sample analysis carried out by the CPR survey, the presence of microplastics has been recorded since 2004, and since 2016 microplastics have been counted and categorised. It should be noted that the plastic data, routinely counted by the CPR survey, have not all been formally identified using spectrometry, but have been recorded using microscopic analysis. In figure 5.2B, the presence of microplastics is mapped (Johns (2020) (Dataset). <https://doi.org/10.17031/1688>), demonstrating that microplastics are found throughout the North Atlantic, even in some of the higher latitude samples in the North West Passage.

Many of the in situ data presented here can be combined with models to interpolate missing areas of data, and predict how distribution might change with currents and changing weather conditions. For example, Eriksen et al. (2014) modelled the distribution of microplastics in the Atlantic Ocean based on surface tows. The data is available online (<http://dx.doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.1015289>) and can be integrated with more recently acquired data. By generating these maps of potential hotspots of marine litter we can demonstrate areas that are more likely to be impacted. The next steps in the analysis are to link these hotspots with available effort data, such as fish abundance, sampling effort and fishing effort. These combined impacts will demonstrate areas of highest risk to these anthropogenic pressure (Kuczynski et al., 2022).

8.1.2. Seabed marine litter

A summary of readily available geospatial information related to seabed litter is presented in the sections below. In terms of global (Atlantic wide) datasets, an interesting project has been undertaken by AWI institute in Germany, which collated data related to litter biota interactions as presented in published sources. They visualised the outputs of this project in the form of online map (Fig. 8.3).

Figure 8.3. Litter biota interactions as recorded from published sources. Data source: https://maps.awi.de/awimaps/projects/public/?cu=litter_biota_interactions#home

8.1.2.1. Seabed marine litter in Norwegian Sea

Limited processed data can be viewed in MAREANO: Seabed litter - Number of litter observations per video transect http://mareano.no/kart/mareano_en.html#maps/4855 (Fig. 8.4). More extensive datasets exist, but are currently unprocessed (Pål Mortensen, personal communications).

Figure 8.4. Litter map in Norwegian Sea. Data source: http://mareano.no/kart/mareano_en.html#maps/4855.

In addition, a dataset for micro-plastics in marine sediments are available for the Norwegian Sea case study area. Data source: <http://metadata.nmdc.no/metadata-api/landingpage/544afecf9fea795426c840a49a50a4c7>.

8.1.2.2. Seabed marine litter in Celtic Sea

Composition and spatial distribution of litter on the seafloor within the Celtic Sea study area can be obtained from OSPAR based on surveys conducted prior to 2017. This data can be downloaded in GIS format (https://odims.ospar.org/en/submissions/ospar_ia2017_seabed_litter_2017_01/). The map presented on Figure 8.5a illustrates relative number of litter items per km² seafloor based on the number of items caught as by-catch in fisheries trawls and Figure 8.6b presents data from EMODnet (<https://www.emodnet-chemistry.eu/products/catalogue#/metadata/e410bd8c-ad38-482b-8a76-d867a40746fc>). Additional information on marine litter in this case study area can be downloaded in GIS format from CEFAS (Figure 8.6).

Figure 8.5. In the top (a), relative number of seabed litter items per square km based on the number of items caught as by-catch in fisheries trawls (OSPAR, 2017). Data source: OSPAR. In the bottom (b), seabed litter from EMODnet portal.

Figure 8.6. Seabed litter in the Celtic Sea study area based on CEFAS surveys. Data source: <https://data.cefas.co.uk/search/1/litter>.

Beach litter in the Celtic Seas primarily consists of plastic fragments, food and drink packaging, fishing-related litter, cotton buds, cigarette butts, rubber balloons and shotgun cartridges (OSPAR 2017). The highest amounts of litter are found in the Southern Celtic Sea (Fig8.6a), 58% of which consist of plastics (OSPAR 2017). Despite this, microplastics in the Celtic Sea surface waters appear to be relatively low compared to regions such as the Pacific gyre, with higher concentrations observed near the coast and river estuaries (Maes et al., 2017).

In 2011 the mean number of macrolitter items in the Celtic Sea were found to be 21.6 km⁻² offshore, and 24.3 km⁻² inshore, consisting of 94% and 77% plastic respectively (Maes et al., 2018). Data from the Irish Groundfish Survey 2010-2014 indicate that litter is present in 57% of offshore sites sampled, plastic made up 84% of the litter encountered, 51% of which could be directly linked to fishing activity (nets, rope, fishing line, gloves, buoys, pots, etc.: Moriarty et al., 2016).

8.2. River discharge and nutrients

A review of available data of river flows and nutrient river discharges for the Atlantic basin has been made. As a result, an inventory of the most relevant data sources found with global extension has been created (Tables 8.I and 8.II).

Table 8.I. Inventory and description of the global river flows datasets identified. The description fields include a brief summary of data content, information on spatial and temporal extents and resolutions and the links to the datasets and scientific reference papers that fully describe them.

Data Source	Summary	Resolution	Data Access	Reference
Global Runoff Data Base (GRDB)	Includes discharge data observations of 10361 gauging stations from all over the world.	Varies for each station. A Station's catalogue is provided with this information. (Less observations are available for earliest years.	GRDC Data Portal (bafg.de)	Global Runoff Data Centre (GRDC) in the Federal Institute of Hydrology (BfG) grdc@bafg.de https://grdc.bafg.de
Global Streamflow Indices and Metadata Archive (GSIM)	A worldwide collection derived from more than 35 000 daily streamflow time series from seven national streamflow databases and five international collections (incl, GRBC).	Varies for each station. Includes data from Global Runoff Data Base.	DOI	Do et al., 2018.
Freshwater Fluxes into the World's Oceans	Continental freshwater input into the oceans from the WaterGAP 2.2d model. Product of the GRDC.	Yearly estimations at different basins and spatial grids between 1901–2016	https://shiny.bafg.de/fwf/Web2	Recknagel et al, 2021
WaterGAP2.2	Raw WaterGAP 2.2d model discharge estimations.	Monthly data on a 0.5° x 0.5° grid between 90°N and 60°S. 1901–2016	https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.918447	Müller Schmied et al. 2020.
GRUN: Gridded runoff dataset	Prediction of runoff rates based on precipitation and temperature reanalysis. Uses the random forest (RF) algorithm (Breiman, 2001)	Monthly estimations between 1902-2014 on 50 km cells.	https://doi.org/10.5194/essd-11-1655-2019, 2019	Ghiggi et al, 2019
UNH/GRDC composite runoff fields v1.0.	Monthly runoff climatologies combining observed river discharge information (from GRBC) with a climate-driven Water Balance Model.	Global Monthly climatologies.	http://www.compo.siter.unoff.sr.unh.edu/	Fekete et al, 2018.
PCR-GLOBWB	PCR-GLOBWB (PCRaster Global Water Balance) is a large-scale hydrological model.	5 arc-minute resolution and 30 arc-minute resolution	https://zenodo.org/record/1045339#.YThgevkzaUk	Sutanudjaja et al, 2017.

Table 8.II. Inventory and description of the global river nutrient discharges datasets identified. The description fields include a brief summary of data content, information on spatial and temporal extents and resolutions and the links to the datasets and scientific reference papers that fully describe them.

Data Source	Summary	Resolution	Data Access	Reference
GRQA: Global River Water Quality Archive	Database aggregating and harmonizing five national, continental and global observation datasets: CESI, GEMSTAT, GLORICH, WATERBASE and WQP.	Depends on station and nutrient. Includes obs. of different forms of N, P and C compounds, although original GEMSTAT, WATERBASE and WQP also include other parameters.	http://dx.doi.org/10.23673/re-273	Virro et al, 2021
GEMSTAT (2018)	Observations	Global, varies for each station.	https://gemstat.org/data/data-portal/	International Centre for Global Water Resources and Global Change.
GLORICH	Observations	Global, varies for each station.	https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.902360	Hartman et al., 2019.
McDowel 2020 Global dataset diffuse riverine	Yearly diffuse loads (kg) and yields (kg ha ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹) of dissolved and total nitrogen and phosphorus forms.	Cover years 2004-2012 for 1,421 catchments.	https://doi.org/10.25400/lincolnuninz.11894697	McDowell, et al, 2020.
Global riverine nitrogen and phosphorus input, retention and export during the 20th century	Estimations from IMAGE-GNM model coupled to the PCR-GLOBWB global hydrological model	Cover years 1900-2000; load and retention of P and N each 5 years.	https://easy.dans.knaw.nl/ui/datasets/id/easy-dataset:64145	Beusen et al, 2016
Global NEWS 2 River Nutrient Exports - Realistic Hydrology Model Run for reference year 2000 ("RH2000")	Modelled annual exports at the mouth of rivers for dissolved (DIN, DIP, DON, DOP, DOC), and particulate nutrients (PN, PP, POC)	Yearly. (1970-2000) and (2030 & 2050)	https://marine.rutgers.edu/globalnews/datasets.htm	Beusen et al. 2009; Seitzinger et al., 2010)
gnc global news model	Predicted changes per basin nutrient fluxes and nutrient form (2000 - 2050) DIN, DIP, DON, PP, PN, DOP	Single Period 2000-2050, Basins.	http://geonode.iwlearn.org/layars/geonode:gnc_global_news_model	Global_Nutrient_Cycle

After examining the contents of these datasets (parameters, temporal ranges, locations, number of observations, methods used etc.), two datasets have been selected as the most “appropriate” datasets for Integrated Ecosystem Assessment:

- 1) For river discharges, the output of the WaterGAP 2.2d model (Monthly data on a 0.5° x 0.5° grid between 90°N and 60°S. 1901–2016) (Müller Schmied et al. 2020) was selected. The main reason for selecting the watergap2.2d outputs is that it offers a very good spatio-temporal extent and resolution, and according to the Müller Schmied et al. 2020, the validation results for streamflow (or discharges values) are reasonably satisfactory, although there is some spatial variability in the performance results. Moreover, the recently published “Global Freshwater Fluxes into the World's Oceans (GRDC, 2021)” product and paper, uses the yearly outcomes of this model, which has also supported this choice.
- 2) For nutrient discharges, the observations from the “Global River Water Quality Archive” (Virro et al, 2021) have been selected because, among the publicly available and downloadable datasets, it gathers the highest number of observations and includes data from different international and national databases.

These selected datasets have been geo-processed to provide global data of coastal runoff and nutrient discharges at a best available spatial and temporal extents and resolutions.

The original **watergap2.2d** data is provided in netcdf format. Our post-processing has included the selection of the coastal cells to select runoff values directly poured from land into the ocean. This selection has been made by intersecting the raster netcdf with a coastline shapefile. Then, the monthly runoff values in these cells have been extracted and exported to a shapefile (Global_YearMonthly_River_flow_watermap22_coast.shp). This shapefile (Fig. 8.7) includes the Date, the latitude and longitude of the coastal cell’s centroids and the runoff values (m^3s^{-1}).

Figure 8.7. Spatial representation overlaid to rivers of order 1 (directly connected to sea) from RiverATLAS v10 (Linke et al., 2019.). Includes the 1901–2016 coastal monthly runoff values from WaterGAP 2.2d model (Müller Schmied et al., 2020).

The original GRQA dataset is provided as csv files (one file for each nutrient). These files have been processed to subset only observations at stations near the coastline. To do this, an intersection between station locations and a buffer of 0.2 degrees around the coastline has been made. (Fig. 8.8).

Figure 8.8. Map of nutrient discharges' observation's locations overlaid to rivers of order 1 (directly connected to sea) from RiverATLAS v10 (Linke et al., 2019). Includes the coastal data from the "Global River Water Quality Archive" (Virro et al., 2021).

8.3. Aquaculture

Although aquaculture can reduce the pressure on wild fish captures, it also introduces other potential pressures such as introduction of exotic species and pathogens, effluent discharge, the use of wild fish to feed farmed fish, habitat destruction, changes in productivity, biodiversity and behavioural changes on wild fauna (Gentry et al., 2017; Naylor, 2006; Tičina et al., 2020). Mapping of aquaculture sites or production areas was based on multiple sources since a unique integrated source has not been found this section focuses only on the case study regions for which data was available (Fig. 8.10).

8.3.1. Aquaculture in Northeast Atlantic

Northeast Atlantic aquaculture in European waters (Fig. 8.9) was compiled from two main sources:

- 1) Individual countries data compiled by PRIMROSE and Euroshell projects for Atlantic areas of Scotland, Ireland, England, France, Spain and Portugal.
- 2) The Harmful Algae Event Database (HAEDAT) <http://haedat.iode.org/>

The aquaculture was categorized in three main groups: shellfish, finfish and algae.

Figure 8.9. A. Spread of shellfish aquaculture production in Atlantic areas of Scotland, Ireland (Northern Ireland not included), England, France, Spain, and Portugal. Individual countries data compiled by PRIMROSE and Euroshell projects for Atlantic areas of Scotland, Ireland, England, France, Spain and Portugal. B. Records of harmful algal events affecting finfish and shellfish aquaculture. These records come from the HAEDAT database.

8.3.2. Aquaculture in the Southern Benguela

Sea-based aquaculture in South Africa operates in only two bays, namely Algoa and Saldanha Bay (Fig. 8.10). The footprint of the current aquaculture operations was used to determine the affected area. Currently, South Africa has nine operational shellfish farms that grow two species of non-native oyster and mussel, *Magallana gigas* (formerly *Crassostrea gigas*) and *Mytilus galloprovincialis* (invasive), respectively. Research focused on the impacts of aquaculture in South Africa highlighted the increased risk of alien species introduction (Haupt et al. 2010; Mead et al. 2011; Bolton et al. 2016). A lack of alien species control when aquaculture organisms are imported and translocated inter-regionally increase the likelihood of their introduction and spread (Haupt 2009). In addition, other research has highlighted the increased risks of pathogen and disease introduction (Bondan-Reantaso et al., 2015) and eutrophication (Lemley et al., 2019).

Figure 8.10. Map of the footprint of sea-based aquaculture operations for Saldanha Bay (left) and Algoa Bay (right).

Aquaculture in South Africa occurs over a very limited area and data on the footprint of existing sea-based aquaculture was used for the NBA2018. A 1-km buffer was applied to aquaculture polygons to develop an aquaculture footprint.

8.3.3. Aquaculture on the South Brazilian Shelf

In southern Brazil, the aquaculture is carried out in coastal areas (depth < 10 m) mainly in Santa Catarina and São Paulo states. At Santa Catarina, mollusk production is the predominant aquaculture (Fig. 8.11). In São Paulo, there are 108 licensed aquaculture sites using floating nets. The aquaculture occupies a tiny area when compared with SBS total area, located at sheltered areas like embayment's and between islands and the continent.

Figure 8.11. Aquaculture sites on the South Brazilian Shelf. The size of the sites has been exaggerated for cartographic purposes. The inset map A shows the floating nets near São Sebastião (São Paulo state) and the map B shows mollusk sites near Florianópolis (Santa Catarina state).

9. Other activities making pressures on bottom communities

A wide variety of human activities occur routinely that have a direct impact on the seabed and the associated bottom communities that live in, on, or above the seabed. Benthic habitats have varying degrees of sensitivity and resilience, which needs to be considered when activities or development plans are proposed that may have long-term impact on biodiversity distribution. This chapter assesses, and where feasible, maps the current status of some human activities that may currently or in the future impact seabed integrity, benthic communities and Vulnerable Marine Ecosystems (VMEs). Where data exist but are not FAIR the source is acknowledged. Where data are inconsistent between Case Studies, recommendations are provided to improve future data collation and mapping, which in some cases may include the need for development of data standards. Data and information were collated from the WP2 Mission Atlantic Data sources inventory, from direct contributions from WP4 & WP3 partners, and from FAIR data identified through internet search engines. Bottom fisheries and seabed litter data are presented in sections 7 and 8 respectively.

9.1. Oil exploitation

Data related to oil exploitation and oil exploration activities, where available, are presented for the relevant case study areas below. Where data were available for download, a map was created using GIS software showing the relevant geospatial information as well as the boundary of the Mission Atlantic case study area. One of the most centralised sources of information related to offshore oil and gas activities in the North Atlantic is available from EMODnet Human Activities data portal (Fig. 9.1), which provides information relevant for two of the Mission Atlantic case study areas, the Norwegian Sea and Celtic Sea.

Figure 9.1. EMODnet Human Activities data portal screenshot of oil and gas exploitation and exploration data, subdivided into: Active Licenses, Boreholes (wells), Offshore Installations. This portal provides data relevant only for two case study areas: Norwegian Sea and Celtic Sea.

9.1.1. Oil exploitation in the Norwegian Sea

This section presents maps of oil and gas licences, wells and offshore installations within the Norwegian Sea case study area. This data can be accessed in GIS format through the EMODnet Human Activities data portal (<https://www.emodnet-humanactivities.eu/view-data.php/>). The data have been downloaded and integrated within a desktop GIS, and the maps presented below were produced showing relevant geospatial information within the Norwegian Sea case study area. Additional information about the history of oil exploration in Norway can be obtained from the Norwegian Government website (<https://www.regjeringen.no/en/topics/energy/oil-and-gas/norways-oil-history-in-5-minutes/id440538/>). Exploration commenced in 1963 when the government confirmed the ownership of the Norwegian Continental Shelf, and started to issue licences allowing companies to perform seismic surveys with a view to evaluating resource potential. In 1965 the first licensing round was announced resulting in 22 production licences for 78 blocks being awarded to oil companies or consortia. Oil production subsequently commenced in 1971. Since that time offshore petroleum has significantly contributed to the economy and welfare of the Norwegian state. The sector is administered by the Oil and Gas Department of the Ministry of Petroleum and Energy.

Figure 9.2. A) Active oil and gas licenses located in the Norwegian Sea case study area. B) Map displaying offshore oil and gas wells (incl. active and suspended exploration wells) within the Norwegian Sea case study area. C) Offshore oil and gas installations located within the Norwegian Sea case study area. Data source: EMODnet Human Activities Data portal.

9.1.2. Oil and gas exploitation in the Celtic Sea

Data regarding oil and gas current authorisations (Fig. 9.3a), exploration including wells (Fig. 9.3b) and seismic surveys (Fig. 9.3c & 9.3d) in the Celtic Sea case study area is available for download in GIS format² through the Integrated Petroleum Affairs System (IPAS) website³. The Department of the Environment, Climate and Communications (DECC) of the Government of Ireland has responsibility for issuing petroleum licences.⁴ Since September 2019 the DECC is no longer accepting new applications for exploration licences for natural oil and gas. This policy change represents part of Ireland's Transition to a Low Carbon Economy. However, all applications and authorisations in place before 23 September 2019 have not been affected by this decision and are allowed to continue. There are no current oil exploitation activities within the Celtic Sea case study area. With regards to offshore gas exploitation, Kinsale Head, Ballycotton and Seven Heads gas fields have reached the end of their productive life in 2020 and are in the process of being decommissioned. The production of gas from Corrib gas field is projected to stop by 2030.

Figure 9.3. Oil exploitation in the Celtic Sea case study area. A) Current oil and gas authorisations as of June 2020. B) Oil and gas exploration wells. C) 2D seismic surveys. D) 3D seismic surveys. Data source: DCCAE.

² [https://www.dccae.ie/en-ie/natural-resources/topics/Oil-Gas-Exploration-Production/data/Pages/Spatial-\(GIS\)-Data.aspx](https://www.dccae.ie/en-ie/natural-resources/topics/Oil-Gas-Exploration-Production/data/Pages/Spatial-(GIS)-Data.aspx)

³ <http://gis.dcenr.gov.ie/internetIPAS/servlet/internet/IPAS2IHome>

⁴ <https://www.gov.ie/en/policy-information/bf1b50-oil-and-gas-exploration-and-production/>

9.1.3. Oil Exploitation in the Canary Current

FAIR data were not located at the time of reporting for Oil exploitation in the Canary Current case study area. It is evident from internet searches that relevant data exist and have been commercially compiled such as the “Offshore West Africa Oil and Gas Map to 2022”, however further work is required to locate, access and collate publicly available data resources. Chapter 4 “Oil and Gas Developments” in the recent report produced by BirdLife provides information (Fig. 9.4) about offshore oil and gas licence blocks of Mauritania and Senegal in active phase of exploration and exploitation (source: <https://heyzine.com/flip-book/ee609baabf.html>).

Figure 9.4. Oil and gas related activities in the area overlapping with Canary Current CS area (source: <https://heyzine.com/flip-book/ee609baabf.html#page/93>)

9.1.4. Oil exploitation in the Southern Benguela

Data collated were sourced from the Petroleum Agency SA under the Department of Mineral Resources, which is responsible for the licencing and permitting of oil and gas activities in South Africa. The data included information on planned, proposed, abandoned, completed, recovered and suspended wells. The highest density of wellheads was found on the Agulhas Bank (Fig. 9.5). Maps presented on Figures x and x show most recent compilation of petroleum exploration and production activities in South Africa (Data source: Petroleum Agency SA <http://www.petroleumagencyrsa.com>). The Petroleum Agency SA also provided free online access to webGIS portal allowing visualisation of information about offshore oil and gas activities https://geoportal.petroleumagencyrsa.com/Storefront/Viewer/index_map.html.

Figure 9.5. Map illustrating footprint of oil and gas related activities (shown in red) within the Benguela Current case study area (shown by black line). SANBI collated points on active and dormant oil and gas well points from the Petroleum Agency South Africa, the local national entity responsible for managing oil and gas development for the country. This data consisted of point data for all active, abandoned, and temporarily suspended wellheads.

Figure 9.6. Map showing most recent compilation of petroleum exploration and production activities in South Africa (Data source: Petroleum Agency SA <http://www.petroleumagencyrsa.com>.)

Figure 9.7. A map from Petroleum Agency SA showing offshore exploration opportunities and highlight geophysical data in the Benguela CS area (Data source: <http://www.petroleumagencyrsa.com>.)

9.1.5. Oil exploitation on the South Brazilian Shelf

Currently, there are only 2 oil platforms operating inside the SBS area (depth < 200 m), but there are 20 other platforms at the Santos Basin (near SBS boundary), accounting for 1/3 of the active oil platforms in Brazil. This continental shelf area is important with pipelines and shipping links between platforms and coastal terminals (ports or monobuoys). There are also licenses for 157 oil and gas exploration blocks sold by the National Oil and Gas Agency (ANP) through 17 bidding rounds to negotiate concessions for oil and gas exploration in Brazil. The blocks sold can be used as a proxy for future exploration scenarios at the SBS. In this context, approximately 15% of SBS area was allocated for future oil and gas exploration (157 blocks).

Figure 9.8. Oil blocks designated and sold by Brazilian government for exploration and exploitation as well as oil platforms. See text for further details. Data source: Brazilian oil agency (ANP) <http://qeo.anp.gov.br>.

9.2. Telecommunications

Data related to seabed deployed telecommunications cables are presented below for the Atlantic Ocean, illustrating that most cables in the north Atlantic are running across the ocean interconnecting Europe and North America, while most seabed cables in the south Atlantic are running along the African continent interconnecting different countries. Such submarine cables were first deployed in the early 1850s, with the first transatlantic communication in August 1858 (Schwartz et al., 2008). The relationship between submarine telecommunications cables and the marine environment is well documented by Carter et al. (2014), and while the footprint of a cable is very narrow, typically 70-150 mm in diameter, the maintenance and burial of exposed cable where required in shallower waters is likely to have more significant environmental impact than its deployment upon the seabed in deep-ocean waters.

Figure 9.9. Telecommunication cables (schematic routes) are available to view and download from the EMODnet Human Activities Data portal. Cables shown by green lines and yellow circles indicate the location of landing stations.

Where data were available for download, a map was created using GIS software showing the relevant geospatial information as well as the boundary of the Mission Atlantic case study area. One of the most centralised sources of information related to offshore oil and gas activities in the North Atlantic is available from EMODnet Human Activities data portal (Fig. 9.1), which provides information relevant for two of the Mission Atlantic case study areas, the Norwegian Sea and Celtic Sea. A global schematic location of telecommunication cables within the Atlantic region can be viewed and downloaded in GIS format from the EMODnet Human Activities Data portal (<https://www.emodnet-humanactivities.eu/view-data.php>). This data has been downloaded and integrated to desktop GIS and the map illustrating the position of cables in relation to the Mission Atlantic case study areas produced (Fig. 9.9). EMODnet also provides some data on the actual position of some telecommunications cables (Fig. 9.10), as opposed to schematic or indicative positions. Global GIS datasets showing schematic cable routes are accessible online (Data source: TeleGeography - <https://www.submarinecablemap.com/>) showing more extensive and current representation of cable infrastructure, particularly in the southern Atlantic (Fig. 9.9).

Figure 9.10. Screenshot from EMODnet Human Activities portal of actual Telecommunications routes (as opposed to schematic) which are available to view and download for some cables.

Figure 9.11. Global schematic location of telecommunication cable routes showing additional cables, particularly in the South Atlantic. Data prepared by TeleGeography and shared through <https://github.com/telegeography/www.submarinecablemap.com>

9.2.1. Telecommunications in the Celtic Sea

Information and data for seabed cables in the Celtic Sea case study are available from the Kingfisher Information Service - Offshore Renewable & Cable Awareness project (KIS-ORCA) (<https://kis-orca.org/downloads/>). Data are collated (Fig 9.12) through an ongoing initiative between the European Subsea Cables Association (ESCA) and the Kingfisher Information Service of Seafish. ESCA membership represents much of the subsea telecommunications and offshore renewable energy industry, and they cooperate and share accurate, up to date and free information relating to subsea cables and offshore renewable energy structures with fishermen, to raise awareness and reduce risk associated with seabed cable infrastructure.

Figure 9.12. Present telecommunications cable routes for the Celtic Sea. Data source: <https://kis-orca.org/downloads/>.

9.2.2. Telecommunications on the South Brazilian Shelf

Submarine cables are located in the northern region of the South Brazilian Shelf CS. Rio de Janeiro and Santos are the main hub cities for telecommunication on this CS (Fig. 9.13). It must be noted, however, that this map was obtained from a global dataset and indicates only the major connections in operation. Navigation charts made available by the Brazilian Navy show a denser network in some locations functioning as local hubs (e.g., Santa Catarina Island, in the central portion of the case study area).

Figure 9.13. Schematic routes of submarine cables in the South Brazilian Shelf case study area, Data source: TeleGeography – <https://www.submarinecablemap.com>

9.3. Scientific exploration

There has been much discussion and research on the impact of oil and gas related seismic survey activity on the marine environment (McCauley et al., 2000), due to the strength of sound energy transmitted from the airgun sources. On the contrary, little is published on the environmental impact of benthic and/or non acoustic seabed related scientific surveys, however detailed guidance has been published on undertaking Marine Scientific Research, in the context of the United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea (United Nations, 2010).

Maps are not provided by Case Study Area for scientific exploration, as while some spatial data are available on where scientific research cruises have taken place in the Atlantic, in the context of WP4 (Benthic Mapping: ecosystem, resources and pressures), the data do not readily show cruises that may impact on the seabed and the associated benthic communities. During MISSION ATLANTIC, efforts will continue to develop research survey metadata records to improve future visibility of the extent of scientific exploration physically interacting with or imaging the seabed.

Some useful research vessel fleet information is available for historical and some planned Atlantic Ocean scientific surveys:

Resource Title: EuroFleets+ - *European Virtual Infrastructure in Ocean Research*

Link to webGIS: https://evior.eurofleets.eu/v_eurofleets_v1/search.asp

Resource Title: University-National Oceanographic Laboratory System (UNOLS) - U.S.

Link to website: <https://www.unols.org/vessel-schedules>

Link to webGIS (current/planned survey locations and metadata accessible):

<https://www.mfp.us/programme/mappage>

The following are some of the individual organisations that provide information on their scientific exploration activity in publicly accessible webGIS format with some surveys overlapping with Mission Atlantic Case Study areas:

Organisation: British Geological Survey (BGS).

Project Title: GEOINDEX OFFSHORE

Link to webGIS: http://mapapps2.bgs.ac.uk/geoindex_offshore/home.html

Organisation: British National Oceanographic Data Centre

Cruise inventory: https://www.bodc.ac.uk/resources/inventories/cruise_inventory/

Organisation: INFOMAR (Geological Survey Ireland (GSI) + Marine Institute)

Project Title: INFOMAR web map service presents metadata for each individual multibeam bathymetry survey)

Links to webGIS: <https://www.infomar.ie/maps/downloadable-maps/surveys-reports-and-metadata>

Organisation: IFREMER (France)

Project Title: SEXTANT. Institutional webGIS maps providing a wealth of information about IFREMER's scientific explorations around the world with some being relevant in the context of Mission Atlantic CS areas.

Link to webGIS: <https://sextant.ifremer.fr/>

IFREMER also has a video catalogue, which presents the seabed video data from around the world – when playing particular video there is a map showing location of that dive. <https://video.ifremer.fr/index>

Organisation: AWI (Germany)

Project Title: maps@awi (lists scientifically prepared data from AWI research in the form of highly adapted WebGIS projects.)

Links to webGIS: <https://maps.awi.de/awimaps/catalog/>

Organisation: NOAA Ocean Exploration

Links to webGIS: <https://oceanexplorer.noaa.gov/explorations/location/explorations-by-location.html>

In the Celtic Sea case study area, GIS data for seismic exploration related to Oil and Gas can be downloaded: [https://www.dccae.ie/en-ie/natural-resources/topics/Oil-Gas-Exploration-Production/data/Pages/Spatial-\(GIS\)-Data.aspx](https://www.dccae.ie/en-ie/natural-resources/topics/Oil-Gas-Exploration-Production/data/Pages/Spatial-(GIS)-Data.aspx).

In the Norwegian case study area, information relating to scientific exploration are provided: <https://www.mareano.no/>.

Marine Institute (Ireland) has internal records of national and foreign research cruises in Ireland's territorial waters. This information is not publicly available in GIS format. Applications for each cruise including names of chief scientists are available on request as well as cruise tracks and cruise reports.

In the North Mid Atlantic Ridge case study area, data are available on the regional government geoportal which includes nine stations (<https://sigmar.dram.azores.gov.pt/#/viewer/openlayers/geoportal>). However, some of them might be buoys or equipment attached to the seabed.

The Mid-Atlantic Ridge (MAR) area, near the Azores, has been a site with in situ observatories for over 20 years in association with various international programs (Colaço et al., 2011).

In the South Brazilian Shelf case study area, scientific exploration effort can be indicatively assessed through retrieval of research cruise logs, and compilation of biological data. Sampling stations have been registered by the Brazilian Navy since the 80's indicating seasonal density of hydrographic data acquired (Fig. 9.14).

Figure 9.14. Hydrographic sampling stations distribution in the South Brazilian Shelf available at the Brazilian National Oceanographic Database (BNDO). Colours refer to the season in which the oceanographic cruise was operated (yellow = autumn; green spring; red = summer; blue = winter). Source: Valente (2019), available at: https://issuu.com/filipefigueiredodaguaia/docs/livro_para_pdf_1

The biological data available from the two global open data access portals, OBIS and GBIF, indicate areas of focussed biological scientific research in the South Brazilian Shelf. Data can be presented as a heatmap (Kernel Density Estimation) for all species, illustrating a high-density coastal sampling area in São Paulo state, as well as data gaps at Paraná state and the northern area of Rio Grande do Sul state (Fig. 9.15).

Figure 9.15. Point Density occurrences (presence) registered at OBIS and GBIF at SBS. Data sources: <https://obis.org> and <https://www.gbif.org/>

9.4. Seabed minerals

Information regarding seabed mineral exploration licensing blocks (seabed Areas Beyond National Jurisdiction (ABNJ)) are hosted by the International Seabed Authority. These blocks are subject to scientific exploration, but no seabed mineral exploitation licenses have been granted. The exploration block areas at the Mid Atlantic Ridge in the North Atlantic and Rio Grande Rise in the South Atlantic can be viewed on the web mapping portal (<https://data.isa.org/im/isa/map/>) but are not readily downloadable. Information regarding potential seabed mineral resources for a number of case study areas is available to view and can be downloaded in GIS format (Fig. 9.16) from the EMODnet Geology Data portal (https://www.emodnet-geology.eu/map-viewer/?p=marine_minerals). It should be noted that some of the locations relate to hydrocarbons and marine aggregates and, not solely seabed mineral potential.

Figure 9.16. Screenshot from EMODnet Geology Data portal showing European marine mineral, aggregate and hydrocarbon distribution.

9.4.1. Seabed minerals in the Norwegian Sea

There are no seabed mineral exploration or exploitation licenses or activities in the Norwegian Sea case study area. The mineral potential dataset available from the EMODnet Geology Data portal only indicates the presence of hydrocarbons and marine aggregates (sand and gravel), thus no map has been presented in this section.

9.4.2. Seabed minerals in the Celtic Sea

There are no seabed mineral exploration or exploitation licenses or activities in the Celtic Sea case study area. The seabed mineral potential data can be viewed and downloaded from the EMODnet Geology Data portal. Mineral deposits primarily related to marine aggregates. The available mineral potential data was downloaded and integrated to desktop GIS and a map was produced (Fig. 9.17).

Figure 9.17. Map displaying data available for download from EMODnet Geology portal showing natural resource distribution in the Celtic Sea study area.

9.4.3. Seabed minerals in the North Mid Atlantic Ridge

There are no seabed mineral exploration or exploitation licenses or activities in the North Mid Atlantic Ridge case study area. Seabed mineral potential is presented for the North Mid Atlantic Ridge case study area based on data from the EMODnet Geology Data portal (Fig. 9.15). These data were integrated to desktop GIS to produce the map below. Additional relevant data about mineral potential are available from a geoportal (<https://sigmar.dram.azores.gov.pt/#/viewer/openlayers/geoportal>) which includes data points on potential seabed mineral resources, including polymetallic sulphides and cobalt-rich ferromanganese (Fig. 9.18).

Figure 9.18. Seabed minerals information sourced from EMODnet portal.

Figure 9.19. Seabed minerals information sourced from Azore's government geoportal <https://sigmar.dram.azores.gov.pt/#/viewer/openlayers/geoportal>.

9.4.4. Seabed minerals in the Canary Current

Seabed mineral potential is presented for the Canary Current case study area. This data was sourced from the EMODnet Geology Data portal, integrated within GIS, and a map was produced (Fig. 9.20). Based on available information there are not believed to be active seabed exploration or exploitation licenses or activities within the extent of this case study area.

Figure 9.20. Seabed minerals information sourced from EMODnet Geology Data portal.

9.4.5. Seabed minerals in the Southern Benguela

The extent and intensity of mining was mapped by building on the South African National Biodiversity Assessment (NBA) 2011 dataset for points and polygons, and including the NBA 2018 land cover data for mining used in the NBA 2018 Terrestrial Report (Skowno et al., 2019). The area of mining was buffered by 500m to account for areas within this distance of a mined area. Various SANBI datasets (including NBA2011 data on mine points, mined polygons from industry, and the NBA 2018 landcover) were used to identify areas that are mined or within 500m of a mine. These were combined into a single layer (120 m pixels). A 500m buffer was applied and developed in a raster environment to identify any areas near mines.

Figure 9.21. Map illustrating footprint of the mineral mining activity (mostly coastal) within the Benguela case study area.

9.4.6. Seabed minerals in South Brazilian Shelf

Information about seabed minerals in Brazilian waters can be obtained from the Brazilian mining agency (ANM) (<https://geo.anm.gov.br/>). This data has been integrated to desktop GIS and presented in the map below to illustrate seabed mineral potential together with active mining within the extent of the South Brazilian Shelf case study area (Fig. 9.22).

Figure 9.22. Map showing areas with seabed mineral mining potential as well as areas with ongoing active mining. Data source: Brazilian mining agency (ANM) <https://geo.anm.gov.br/>.

The South Brazilian Shelf has seabed resource interests including coal, heavy minerals, limestone, phosphorite, sand and scandium. Currently, there are 521 active mining processes in this CS area (last update in December, 2021), of which 51% relate to aggregate (sand). Most of these processes (40%) are at the research authorization phase, and 10% are currently being explored. Most active mining processes are coastal (depth < 50 m) and only one process is located at the outer continental shelf (200 m), dedicated to research on phosphorite mining (Fig. 9.23).

Figure 9.23. Map of seabed resource interests by type of resource.

10. Conclusions

In this section the report makes some conclusions on the status of mapping widely distributed sectors, the role of big data and machine learning in the whole Atlantic Ocean data integration context, and highlight the additional steps that need to be taken to progress from activities to pressures mapping.

10.1. Mapping widely distributed sectors

Fishing intensity by main groups of fishing gears has been estimated by supervised classification of Automatic Identification System (AIS) data. These approaches have been able to distinguish between fishing and routing activity of individual vessels, while assigning up to 7 main fishing gear types. These are aggregated here into pelagic and bottom fishing activities to match the grouping of ecosystem components in these two groups. AIS data is most useful in the high seas since in coastal areas, smaller vessels do not require AIS, except in some regions of Europe.

Shipping global patterns, inferred from AIS data, reveal that highest shipping intensity is concentrated in coastal areas with narrow routes connecting Asia, Africa and Europe. Connectivity between these continents and America is broader with a medium intensity over large areas. This can be observed in the Europe connection with North America, Europe connection to South America, South Africa connection with South America and in the connection of Asia with North America and with Australia. At the Atlantic scale, the areas of highest shipping intensity are concentrated in European coastal waters.

Concerning pollution, we focus on three main sources: 1) Marine litter (widespread diffuse input), and in particular plastics (microplastics and macroplastics) and 2) Aquaculture platforms, as proxy of marine pollution sources (point source). feed, leading to major environmental concerns. 3) River discharges and nutrients (in between widespread and point source). Although river discharge and associated nutrients are a natural pressure in the coastal environment, anthropogenically polluted rivers can significantly alter the health of marine ecosystems, especially as metallic pollutants are associated with sediments. Open litter data is sparse and focused mainly on European waters. Continuous Plankton Recorder, which can also be used to sample plastics, covers not only European waters, but also an important part of Northwest Atlantic area. After revising multiples sources of river discharges and nutrients discharges the WaterGAP 2.2d model and the Global River Water Quality Archive have been identified as the best sources of data at the Atlantic Ocean and global scales. Aquaculture data is very limited even in European open datasets and it can be addressed applying machine learning to satellite data.

Seabed related data include oil exploitation, telecommunications, scientific exploration and seabed minerals. These data are integrated for European waters in EMODnet Seabed Habitats. In the Norwegian Sea, Celtic Sea, Benguela Current and South Brazilian Shelf additional local sources of oil exploitation data were available. In terms of telecommunications data, published data are predominantly landing stations and schematic routes. Regarding accurate spatial data on scientific surveys, only a few openly available sources have been identified at national and regional levels. Seabed mineral potential has been collated by EMODnet Seabed Habitats for most of the case study areas, except for the Benguela Current where local data were provided. Additional seabed mineral data were also provided for the South Brazilian Shelf, North Mid Atlantic Ridge and Benguela Current case study areas.

10.2. The role of big data and machine learning to map sectors activities

Ocean monitoring by satellite and in situ platforms has increased exponentially during the last few decades (Sajjad and Rehman, 2021). However, a lack of integration of data from multiple observational platforms at appropriate scales and limited real-time processing capacity has until recently prevented the development of effective system for interpreting and employing this wealth of data. The term ‘big data’ was coined to capture the meaning of this emerging trend (Hu et al., 2014). In addition to its sheer volume, big data exhibit other unique characteristics when compared with traditional data. For instance, big data are commonly unstructured and require real-time analysis. The ability for real-time storage, processing and visualization is crucial for an effective system beyond previous proofs-of-concept. This development calls for new system architectures for data acquisition, transmission, storage, and large-scale data processing mechanisms from computer science (LeCun et al., 2015). Big data techniques enhanced by machine learning methods can increase the use of such data and their applicability to ecosystem-based management.

Machine learning has already proven its potential in marine sciences. It has been applied, for example, to fisheries forecasting (Fernandes et al., 2010), automatic classification of zooplankton samples (Fernandes et al., 2009; Irigoien et al., 2009), identification of schools of particular species of fish in acoustic survey data (Mannocci et al., 2021) and sonar (Uranga et al., 2017), litter classification (Cózar et al. 2014; Lorenzo-Navarro et al. 2018) and litter forecasting (Granado et al. 2019). However, if artificial intelligence (AI) methods are not fit for purpose, then trade-offs to accomplish appropriate performances can be missed (Fernandes et al., 2009) or overfitting can lead to over confidence on AI capacity (Fernandes et al., 2010) if proper validation is not performed. A multi-disciplinary approach where the domain experts and AI experts work together is key for enabling this fit -or-purpose AI that can go beyond the state-of-the-art in more than one discipline (Fernandes et al., 2013; Hernández-González et al., 2019). An intermediary approach can be key for a successful process. The intermediary may be an ecologist with interest in statistics and machine learning (Grosjean et al. 2004; Fernandes et al. 2012; Trifonova et al. 2015; Uusitalo et al. 2016), or a person with computing or statistical background with interest in not only developing new algorithms and identifying diverse problems to test them. It is particularly important not to be overconfident about the capacity of algorithms within a limited dataset (Kroodsmas et al. 2019) when the broad picture of the domain to be address can be missed and their applicability limited without proper domain testing beyond statistical validation (Taconet et al. 2019; Lekunberri et al. 2021).

This report highlights big data- and machine learning-based datasets that are available to perform assessments at the level of the whole Atlantic Ocean. These datasets focus on the activities that impact open-ocean marine environments (shipping, fishing and litter) and more coastal areas specific (river discharges and flows, and the growing aquaculture activity). For example, AIS and VMS data are often extensively processed using ML to identify vessel and gear types (Russo et al. 2011, Kroodsmas et al., 2018, Marzuki et al., 2018, Fernandes et al., 2019, Taconet et al., 2019) or fishing vs. non-fishing behaviours (Bertrand et al. 2008; Behivoke et al., 2021). In the worldwide mapping by Global Fishing Watch, Kroodsmas et al. (2018) trained an AI algorithm with AIS data to identify fishing vs non-fishing behaviors and fishing gear types, producing the first map of the global footprint of fisheries (Taconet et al., 2019).

Data collected by Sentinel satellites can be downloaded from the Copernicus Open Access Hub or Alaska Satellite Facility Data Search to identify potential aquaculture sites (Ballester-Berman et al. (2018). Three of the five data files extracted from the Sentinel-1 satellites can be used for aquatic structure detection: (1) the VH band (the satellite emits waves with horizontal polarization and receives them with vertical polarization), (2) the VV band (the satellite emits and detects waves in vertical polarization) and (3) the elevation in meters of each pixel. The first step to detect possible aquaculture zones is to eliminate all non-marine zones. The intensity Dual-Polarization Ratio Anomaly Detector (iDPoIRAD) algorithm can be used to detect aquaculture sites. This algorithm been previously used with Sentinel-1 observations to detect icebergs (Marino et al., 2016). It searches for areas of high contrast between the two polarized wave bands. Once the algorithm is applied, outliers are discarded applying a threshold and potential aquaculture zones can be detected (Fig. 10.1).

Figure 10.1. Image of a test zone after applying the iDPoIRAD algorithm. Land in green, sea in black and possible zones of aquaculture in white. The red dots are the center of the detected zones. In this example, all detections but the smallest one that is not in the border are aquaculture zones.

10.3. Gaps in mapping ecosystem pressures: from activities to pressures

There is a need to progress from mapping sectoral footprints to understanding the spatial footprint of the pressures they create. The differentiation between fishing and non-fishing (e.g. routing) activities of fishing vessels as well as distinguishing the fishing gear is needed to go from mapping activities to the pressures. For example, a fishing vessel en route to a fishing site will generate different levels and types of noise and emissions than it will whilst fishing. Noise and emissions will also differ depending on the fishing gear being used. Furthermore, during fishing is when there is the highest direct pressure exerted on the ecosystem due to the removal of fish, bycatch and litter generation from losing fishing gears. For example, abandoned, lost or discarded litter can be estimated from fishing activity (Kuczynski et al., 2021). Machine learning has been used to classify vessel type by the recorded noise (Santos-Domínguez, 2016). This implies that it might be possible to map the noise pressure based on AIS databases. A recent study estimated underwater noise worldwide based on vessel type and their speed inferred from AIS data (Jalkanen et al., 2021). Integrated assessments require also the mapping of the benefits (McKuinn et al., 2021). For example, fisheries provide food security, employment, income and a range of cultural and heritage services worldwide, whereas shipping reduces global emissions and air contamination in human populated areas in comparison with other modes of transportation.

Members of ICES working group WGSHP are actively working on the development of a conceptual framework for mapping the pressures and impacts of shipping. WGSHP builds upon previous models to develop a holistic framework for shipping based on previous efforts from Canada (Hannah et al. 2020), and Europe (Moldanová et al., 2021; Ytreberg et al., 2021). The Pathways of Effects framework (Hannah et al. 2020) divides shipping into sub-activities, stressors and potential effects. Two European studies (Moldanová et al., 2018 and 2021; Ytreberg et al., 2021) are based on the combination of vessel activity data (AIS) and development of emission and discharge factors from different ship types, originating from the Ship Traffic Emission Assessment Model (STEAM; Jalkanen et al., 2009). STEAM delivers georeferenced data in terms of emissions to air from exhausts, leakage of specific substances from antifouling paints, volumes of liquid waste streams, and energy/noise. The idea behind the European works is to delineate the pressures and stressors identified from different onboard systems to the Descriptors identified in the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD). The approach builds upon a classic DPSIR (Driver-Pressure-State-Impact-Response) framework, and the pressure categories and sub-categories were further refined by Ytreberg et al. (2021).

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Project website	www.missionatlantic.eu		

Deliverable	N°	D3.2	Title	Maps of present ecosystem pressures (fishing, shipping, pollution)
Work Package	N°	3, 4	Title	Pelagic Mapping: ecosystem, resources and pressures
Work Package Leader	AZTI (G. Chust) & USTA (A. Brierley)			
Work Participants	AZTI, MI, USTA, MBA, IMAR, UCT, SAMB, UFSC, USP, IEO, VMDC, VLIZ			

Lead Beneficiary	AZTI, 3
Authors	<p>Jose A. Fernandes, AZTI, jfernandes@azti.es Maria Mateo, AZTI, mmateo@azti.es Yolanda Sagarminaga, AZTI, ysagarminaga@azti.es Xabier Lekunberri, AZTI, xlekunberri@azti.es Thomas Furey, MI, thomas.furey@marine.ie Maxim Kozachenko, MI, geocoast.ireland@gmail.com Debbi Pedreschi, MI, Debbi.Pedreschi@Marine.ie Roland Proud, USTA, rp43@st-andrews.ac.uk Clare Ostle, MBA, claost@mba.ac.uk Inês Gomes, IMAR, istgomes@gmail.com Diana Serrano, IMAR, dianaserranot@gmail.com Christopher Pham, IMAR, phamchristopher@gmail.com Pedro Afonso, IMAR, pafonsopim@gmail.com Lynne Shannon, UCT, lynne.shannon@uct.ac.za Kerry Sink, SANB, K.Sink@sanbi.org.za Lisa Skein, SANB, L.Skein@sanbi.org.za Prideel Majiedt, SANB, P.Majiedt@sanbi.org.za Vitor Alberto Souza, UFSC, cambucisv89@gmail.com Marinez Eymael Garcia Scherer, UFSC, marinezscherer@gmail.com Maria A. Gasalla, USP, mgasalla@usp.br Tiago Borges Ribeiro Gandra, UFSC, prof.tiago.gandra@gmail.com Sergio R. Floeter, USFSC, sergio.floeter@ufsc.br Jarbas Bonetti, USFSC, jarbas.bonetti@gmail.com Eduardo Ramirez, IEO, eduardo.ramirez@ieo.es Marcos Llope, IEO, marcos.llope@ieo.es Andrew Brierley, USTA, asb4@st-andrews.ac.uk Guillem Chust, AZTI, gchust@azti.es</p>
Reviewers	<p>Julian Burgos, HAFRO, julian.burgos@hafogvatn.is Patricia Cabrera, VMDC, patricia.cabrera@VLIZ.be Fabio Sacchetti, Marine, fabio.sacchetti@Marine.ie Patrizio Mariani, DTU, pat@aqua.dtu.dk</p>

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